

Ethics protocol for the *fAlces* project

“*fAlces* – Facial Recognition Technologies. Etho-Assemblages and Alternative Futures” – ERC Advanced Grant n.º 101140664

fAIces
Facial Recognition Technologies.
Etho-Assemblages and Alternative Futures

Ethics Protocol

Advanced grant n. ° 101140664

December 2025

fAIces – Ethics Protocol

Project Title

Facial Recognition Technologies. Etho-Assemblages and Alternative Futures

Funding Agency

European Research Council

Grant ID

101140664

Principal Investigator

Helena Machado

Centre for Research and Studies in Sociology (CIES-Iscte), University Institute of Lisbon

Host Institution

Associação Iscte Conhecimento e Inovação – Centro de Valorização e Transferência de Tecnologias (CVTT-ISCTE)

Duration

01/03/2025 – 28/02/2030

Table of Contents

Explanatory Note on the Integration of DPO Guidance and ERC Ethics Screening Requirements	1
1. Overview of Methodological Scope and Risk Context.....	1
2. Implementation of Modular and Context-Specific Submissions	1
3. Response to ERC Ethics Screening and Data Protection Recommendations	2
4. Reaffirmation of GDPR Principles and Data Security.....	3
Description of the project.....	5
1. Project Rationale and Conceptual Framework.....	5
2. Ethical Dimensions of the Project.....	5
3. Methodology	6
4. Ethical Safeguards for Research Involving Human Participants	7
4.1. Specific Safeguards for Vulnerable Participants – Subproject 4: Black Communities	7
5. Data Protection and GDPR Compliance	8
5.1. Personal Data Handling.....	8
5.2. Pseudonymisation and Storage	9
5.3. International Data Transfers.....	10
5.4. Data Lifecycle	10
6. Ethical Approval and Oversight.....	11
6.1. Authorisations	11
6.2. Ethical Guidelines	11
7. Informed Consent and Information Sharing	11
7.1. Participant Information	11
7.2. Consent Process	12
7.3. Debriefing and Post-Participation Communication	12
8. Potential for Misuse and Mitigation Measures	12
9. Benefit-Sharing and Community Engagement	13
10. Ethical Monitoring and Responsibilities	14
11. Team Roles and Access to Personal Data	14
12. Addendum: Clarifications on Data Protection Measures (as per DPO guidance)	15
12.1. Duty of Information in Use of Public Data (e.g., Web Crawling)	15
12.2. International Data Transfers to/from Countries Without Adequacy Decisions	16
12.3. Confidentiality Agreements for Non-Employed Team Members and External Service Providers	17
Annexes.....	18
Annex 1 - Subproject 1	19
Annex 1A. Participant Information Sheet.....	20
Annex 1B. Consent Form.....	22
Annex 1C. Data Collection Instrument (Interview Guide – Scientists).....	24
Annex 2 - Subproject 2	26
Annex 2A. Participant Information Sheet.....	27
Annex 2B. Consent Form.....	29
Annex 2C. Data Collection Instrument (Interview Guide – Start-Up Professionals)	31
Annex 3 - Subproject 3	33
Annex 3A. Participant Information Sheet.....	34
Annex 3B. Consent Form.....	37
Annex 3C. Data Collection Instrument (Interview Guide – Advocacy Groups / Activists) ..	39
Annex 4 - Subproject 4	40

Annex 4A. Outline for Local Ethical Support.....	41
Annex 4B. Participant Information Sheet (Focus group).....	43
Annex 4C. Consent Form (Focus group)	46
Annex 4D. Focus Group Interview Guide (Black Communities).....	48
Annex 4E. Participant Information Sheet (Videos)	51
Annex 4F. Consent Form (Videos)	54
Annex 4G. Video Interview Guide (Black Communities).....	56
Annex 5 - Subproject 5	57
Annex 5A. Participant Information Sheet.....	58
Annex 5B. Consent Form.....	61
Annex 5C. Data Collection Instrument (Interview Guide – Artists).....	63
Annex 6 - Observation Protocol – Scientific, Technological, Activist, and Artistic Events	65
Annex 7 - Privacy and Ethics Notice for Public Online Data Collection (Web Crawling Activities).....	68
Annex 8 - Data Protection and Cookies Policy (website).....	70
Annex 9A - Confidentiality and Responsibility Agreement for External Service Providers.....	72
Annex 9B - Request of Technical and Legal Approval	74
Annex 10 - Institutional Confidentiality and Responsibility Term for Researchers/Students...	78
Annex 11 - Team Roles and Access to Personal Data	84
Annex 12 - Data Management Plan	86
Annex 13 - Unexpected Findings Procedure and Disclosure Policy (fAICES)	94
Annex 14 - ERC Ethics Summary Report.....	99
Annex 15 - Data Protection Officer’s Opinion	105

Explanatory Note on the Integration of DPO Guidance and ERC Ethics Screening Requirements

Following the preliminary review of the general ethics protocol submitted on 6 March 2025 and the subsequent opinion issued by the Data Protection Officer (DPO) on 3 December 2025 (Annex 15), as well as in light of the requirements identified in the ERC ethics screening (Annex 14), we hereby submit an updated version of the ethics protocol for the *fAIces* project. This version incorporates the requested clarifications, safeguards and supporting documents, with a view to ensuring alignment with the principles of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the ERC ethics framework and the institutional guidelines of Iscte–University Institute of Lisbon.

1. Overview of Methodological Scope and Risk Context

The *fAIces* project involves a diverse range of empirical methods — including semi-structured interviews, focus groups, digital and face-to-face ethnographic observation, and web crawling — and engages multiple participant groups across five subprojects. Overall, the project is expected to involve approximately 250–340 adult participants (≥ 18 years). This includes around 60–80 scientists and academic researchers working on facial technologies; 20–30 professionals from start-ups and AI companies; 20–30 members of civil society organisations and activists; participants in three focus groups per country in seven countries (Germany, Spain, France, the UK, Brazil, Canada and the US), each group with approximately 6–8 Black community members across age cohorts; and 20–30 artists working with facial images. These figures are indicative and may be adjusted as fieldwork progresses. Given the diversity of methods, settings and inclusion of potentially vulnerable populations, the project has adopted a phased and modular ethics compliance strategy, as recommended.

2. Implementation of Modular and Context-Specific Submissions

In line with the Data Protection Officer’s (DPO) preliminary comments of 6 March 2025 and subsequent opinion of 3 December 2025, this protocol adopts a modular and context-specific approach to ethical and data-protection oversight. For each subproject and data-collection method, project-specific materials are prepared and, where appropriate, submitted in advance for review. These include:

- Tailored participant information sheets (annexes 1A, 2A, 3A, 4B, 4E, 5A) and consent forms (annexes 1B, 2B, 3B, 4C, 4F, 5B).
- Context-specific data-collection instruments, including interview guides (annexes 1C, 2C, 3C, 5C), focus-group protocols (annex 4D), video-recording guides (annex 4G) and observation templates (annex 6).
- Detailed descriptions of the technical and organisational safeguards applied to each subproject.

Following the DPO’s opinion of 3 December 2025 (attached as Annex 15), this version of the protocol and its annexes have been revised to implement the additional safeguards recommended therein. In particular, all participant information sheets now explicitly

identify Iscte – University Institute of Lisbon as the data controller and provide a project-specific contact e-mail; clarify that withdrawal of consent does not affect the lawfulness of processing already carried out; describe the secure and separate storage and timely deletion of consent forms and recruitment data; specify that only institutionally licensed tools and services (including cloud solutions where applicable) will be used; set out conditions for international data transfers and for open-science sharing of fully anonymised data; and clarify the legal framework for web-crawling activities and the use of external service providers bound by GDPR-compliant data-processing agreements.

The data-collection instruments submitted with this protocol are intended to serve as the final versions. However, as the team is still engaged in preparatory work and in view of the early stages of implementation, revisions may occur if deemed necessary. Any substantial updates to information sheets, consent forms or instruments, or the introduction of new data-collection procedures, will be documented and, where relevant, re-submitted to the Ethics Committee and/or DPO at Iscte – University Institute of Lisbon.

This modular approach, together with the additional safeguards implemented in response to the DPO’s opinion, ensures that all data-collection activities are subject to appropriate, context-sensitive risk assessment and ethical oversight, and that the residual risks associated with the project remain at an acceptable level in line with GDPR and Iscte’s institutional guidelines.

3. Response to ERC Ethics Screening and Data Protection Recommendations

This protocol reflects the recommendations issued during the ERC ethics screening following the award of the *fAIces* project (ERC Advanced Grant No. 101140664) (see Annex 14). In addition to integrating Iscte–University Institute of Lisbon’s institutional requirements, we have incorporated the three specific clarifications requested by the Data Protection Officer (DPO) in relation to data processing and transfers. These are summarised below:

(i) Duty to Inform in Web Crawling Activities

A Privacy and Ethics Notice has been developed in accordance with Article 14 of the GDPR (annex 7). It will be publicly available on the official *fAIces* project website and referenced in the Data Protection and Cookies Policy (annex 8). This notice outlines:

- The purpose of data collection.
- Categories of personal data involved.
- The legal basis for processing.
- Retention periods.
- Rights of data subjects.
- Contact information for inquiries.

This ensures transparency for individuals whose data may be indirectly collected from publicly accessible online sources (e.g., blog posts, social media, press articles). In cases where direct notification would involve disproportionate effort, a justification under Article 14(5)(b) GDPR has been documented, following best practices in research ethics.

(ii) International Data Transfers to Non-Adequate Countries

For data collection in countries without an EU adequacy decision (e.g., the United States, Brazil), all consent procedures have been updated to include:

- Explicit, informed consent to international data transfers.
- Clear communication of any risks due to differing legal protections.
- Reference to safeguards such as Standard Contractual Clauses (SCCs).

These provisions are now embedded in all relevant participant information sheets and consent forms. Additionally, in accordance with the ERC requirement, local ethics/research approvals will be sought in each country where Subproject 4 fieldwork takes place (including Spain, France, Germany, the UK, USA, Brazil, and Canada) (Annex 4A).

(iii) Confidentiality Agreements and Contracts with Third Parties

All members of the research team who do not have an employment contract with Iscte – University Institute of Lisbon (such as students, research assistants or visiting scholars formally associated with the project) and who have access to personal data will sign Iscte’s Institutional Confidentiality and Responsibility Term for Researchers/Students (Annex 10) before accessing any identifiable or sensitive research data. These collaborators act under the authority of Iscte as data controller and are subject to the same internal rules and training on data protection as employed staff.

By contrast, where external service providers (for example, professional translators or transcribers, or facilitators hired to support focus groups) process personal data on behalf of Iscte and in accordance with its documented instructions, they will sign a specific Confidentiality and Responsibility Agreement for External Providers (Annex 9A) and a written data processing contract or equivalent legal instrument under Article 28 GDPR. These contracts were prepared with the support of the Research Support Office (GAI) and requested to be validated by Iscte’s Legal Office (Annex 9B). The agreements set out in Annexes 9 and 10 do not replace the Article 28 instruments required for data processors.

4. Reaffirmation of GDPR Principles and Data Security

The updated protocol maintains the project's original commitments to:

- Pseudonymisation of personal data at the earliest possible stage.
- Data minimisation and collection limited to essential research purposes.
- Encryption and secure local storage.
- Restricted access only to the Principal Investigator and designated members of the core research team.

- Data retention limited to two years after project completion.
- Full respect for data subject rights, including withdrawal and erasure.

The revised ethics protocol reflects the *fAICES* team's continued commitment to upholding the highest standards of data protection, research ethics, and institutional compliance. We appreciate the DPO's constructive guidance and remain available for any additional clarification or documentation required.

Description of the project

1. Project Rationale and Conceptual Framework

Facial recognition technologies collect billions of faces that are stored for multiple uses spanning individual identification and tracking, to training of deep neural networks, the mainstay of modern artificial intelligence (AI). From tagging a photo on social media or unlocking a computer, to controversial applications of facial recognition in public spaces, schools, workplaces, and law enforcement activities, facial processing technologies have entered almost every aspect of our lives. While expected benefits relate to security and safety, critics highlight that these technologies normalise surveillance and erode privacy, exacerbate discrimination, and contain insurmountable flaws and inaccuracy. The *fAIces* project asks: What matters in facial recognition technologies, and why? How politics of mattering enact diverse ways of being implicated? Which forms of citizenship and public engagement are affected? How multiple and complex ethical choices emerge?

This study develops a novel methodology by which the perspectives of social groups that have never been studied together, which are jointly but antagonistically implicated in facial recognition technologies, are taken into consideration: scientists who conduct research on facial recognition; professionals working in start-ups and technology companies; members of advocacy groups and activists; Black communities; and artists who incorporate facial recognition in their work. The *fAIces* project will produce an innovative social theory of the face through the combination of a new conceptual approach – “etho-assemblages”, which transgresses the idea of pre-given fixed and dichotomic ethical principles – and the generation of original empirical data. Major outcomes are based on expanding ethics and imagining alternative futures, fuelling citizenship and public engagement, and fostering opportunities for academic thinking to be inspired by activism, underrepresented groups, and artistic practices.

2. Ethical Dimensions of the Project

The *fAIces* project explores how facial recognition technologies intersect with ethics, identity, and public life by capturing the perspectives of diverse social actors—scientists, tech entrepreneurs, artists, advocacy groups, and especially Black communities in Europe and the Americas. While these technologies promise safety and efficiency, they raise profound human rights concerns around surveillance, privacy erosion, systemic bias, and algorithmic discrimination. The project aims to interrogate these concerns and co-produce knowledge that centres underrepresented voices. This ethically grounded objective justifies the need to include potentially vulnerable populations and ensure their perspectives directly inform public discourse and alternative socio-technical futures.

3. Methodology

The project adopts a method of situational analysis (Clarke et al., 2018) aiming “thick analyses” explicitly taking into account the full array of elements in the research situation (human, non-human, discursive and material elements) and provoking analysis of relations among them. In particular, for a deeper understanding of the positioning of the diverse social groups, the *fAIces* will examine variations, differences, commonalities, silences, visibilities, invisibilities, conditionality and complexity articulated by social actors when taking a stake on facial recognition technologies. A diversified set of research techniques – document analysis, web crawling, semi-structured individual interviews, focus groups, and ethnographic observation – will be developed. The different types of research data produced through multiple data collection methods will complement one other. The *fAIces* project is organised into three phases that built on top of each other: background; fieldwork; and integration.

Phase 1 (Year 1) – Background: Drawing upon desk research, the first year of the project will be dedicated to elaborating a descriptive overview of facial recognition technologies in Europe and in America, and to designing the theoretical and methodological frameworks. The team will elaborate a visual mapping of the “journeys” of facial recognition technologies, to identify sites of practice, the institutions, organisations, projects and social actors involved, and the places and connections between them. With the support of computer tools (NVivo and Adobe Illustrator), this visual map identifies the networks engaging facial recognition technologies through and between each subproject. The relevant networks will be selected for the work to be developed in phase 2. Selection is intended to maximise diversity and allow theoretical saturation.

Phase 2 (Years 2-4) – Fieldwork across a series of subprojects designed to cross-fertilise each other. The *fAIces* does not have a predefined geographical scope for subprojects 1-3, and 5, since the communities of science, start-ups and companies, advocacy groups, and artistic movements are international. The sites of research will be physical (for example, attending AI and ICT conferences, technological fairs, artistic exhibitions; interviews in person) but also virtual (web crawling and digital ethnography will be used). The subproject 4, with Black communities, will be conducted in particular national contexts, involving focus groups conducted in Europe (France, Germany, Spain, and the UK) and in America (Brazil, Canada, and the US). The selection of countries is based on three criteria: 1. Social, cultural, and historical diversity; 2. Prominence of facial recognition surveillance according to available empirical data; 3. Feasibility: I have contacts in these countries.

Phase 3 (Year 5) – Integration: To create a novel social theory of the face based on original empirical data aimed for an in-depth understanding of the networks of technologies, objects, people, ideas and practices composing the journeys and social life of facial recognition technologies. This final phase of the project provides an innovative understanding of ethics and alternative futures, of citizenship and public engagement, and how academic thinking might be inspired by activism, underrepresented groups, and artistic work.

4. Ethical Safeguards for Research Involving Human Participants

- All participants are adults and volunteers.
- The project includes both non-vulnerable professionals (e.g., scientists, entrepreneurs, artists) and participants from potentially vulnerable populations (e.g., black communities affected by racialised surveillance).
- No financial incentives will be offered to safeguard the voluntary nature of participation. Cost related participation will be covered by the project, aiming to ensure that participants' financial constraints will not impede involvement in the research.

4.1. Specific Safeguards for Vulnerable Participants – Subproject 4: Black Communities

Subproject 4 involves research with Black communities in Europe (France, Germany, Spain, the United Kingdom), and in America (Brazil, Canada, and the United States). Given the historical and ongoing marginalisation of these groups, this subproject will be conducted with heightened ethical sensitivity, aligning with international and local frameworks for the protection of human subjects.

The following safeguards will be implemented:

Local Approvals and Regulatory Compliance

Fieldwork will begin only after securing relevant ethics or institutional approvals in each country, including where required by the European Research Council Executive Agency (ERCEA).

Trusted Intermediaries and Community Partnerships

Access to communities will be facilitated through collaboration with local organisations, community leaders, and grassroots groups. These intermediaries will act not only as facilitators but also as co-creators of knowledge, ensuring the research reflects community values and concerns.

Co-Design and Cultural Appropriateness

Research instruments (interview guides, focus group protocols) will be co-developed with community input to ensure linguistic and cultural relevance. This participatory approach will shape the entire research process.

Addressing Power Imbalances

Informal pre-engagement sessions and co-facilitation of focus groups by trained community members will help build mutual trust and reduce hierarchical dynamics.

Psychosocial Support and Participant Wellbeing

Participants will be informed of their right to pause, skip questions, or withdraw at any point. Signs of distress will be addressed sensitively, and referrals to support services will be provided where appropriate.

Devolution of Results and Community Benefit

Research findings will be returned to the communities through accessible and culturally sensitive formats. This includes multilingual, publicly available summary reports and short, co-produced videos aimed at explaining key insights to a broad audience. These materials will be designed with input from participants and local collaborators to reflect community priorities and ensure knowledge is meaningfully shared. Where possible, community dissemination events or online forums will be organised to foster dialogue around the findings.

Benefit-Sharing Actions

In light of the inclusion of participants from potentially vulnerable populations, a set of benefit-sharing actions will be implemented to ensure ethical reciprocity. These include the development of alternative knowledge transfer mechanisms, such as short educational videos and visual summaries, to explain findings to diverse audiences. These materials will acknowledge cultural specificities and help increase the visibility of the lived experiences and needs of these populations. Participants and community partners will also be invited to suggest other locally appropriate methods for sharing outcomes and fostering community benefit.

In cases where participants wish to be identified by name or image in scientific or public outputs, the research team will conduct an additional ethical assessment. This includes discussing with the participant the potential risks (e.g. public exposure, professional or community repercussions) and documenting their informed decision. The PI retains the right to decline identifiable publication if the risks are deemed disproportionate.

5. Data Protection and GDPR Compliance

5.1. Personal Data Handling

- The project will collect minimal, non-sensitive personal data: name (later pseudonymised), gender, educational/professional background, and current occupation.
- No personal data will be collected beyond what is necessary for the research purposes described in this protocol. The project does not collect or process health, religious, or political data as research variables. The project does not process biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person (GDPR Article 9). Where image/voice may be recorded (Subproject 4 optional co-produced video component), this is done solely with explicit consent and only for the agreed communication/dissemination purposes, not for identification, authentication, or facial recognition.
- Image, audio, or video recordings will only be made with prior, documented informed consent in a secure manner using offline devices. Participants will be clearly informed about their use and rights.

- In Subproject 4, where data revealing racial or ethnic origin may be relevant to the research objectives, such data will only be collected when essential, ethically justified, and with explicit, informed consent, in full compliance with Article 9 of the GDPR.

5.2. Pseudonymisation and Storage

- *Pseudonymisation*: All identifiable data will be pseudonymised as early as possible. Linking keys will be stored securely and separately.
- *Secure Storage*: Data will be stored exclusively in the PI's office at Iscte–University Institute of Lisbon, using encrypted, offline devices, in strict compliance with GDPR and relevant national regulations. Identifiable personal data will not be stored on external commercial cloud services. Data will be stored only on encrypted devices and on institutional servers and licensed cloud services provided by Iscte (for example, Microsoft 365 / Microsoft Teams), which are protected by contractual and technical safeguards.
- *Access and Confidentiality*:

Research team members

Access to personal data is restricted to the Principal Investigator and authorised members of the research team (research fellows, PhD and Master's students, and academic collaborators formally associated with the project). These team members act under the responsibility of Iscte as data controller, receive training on data protection and research ethics, and sign internal confidentiality and responsibility undertakings. Students, visiting researchers and other scientific collaborators without an employment contract with Iscte sign the Institutional Confidentiality and Responsibility Term for Researchers/Students (Annex 10) before accessing any personal data.

External service providers (e.g. translators, transcribers, focus group facilitators)

In specific cases, external service providers may assist the project and have access to personal data (for example, to translate or transcribe interviews or to facilitate focus groups). These providers will act strictly under the documented instructions of Iscte and will be bound by appropriate data processing agreements and confidentiality obligations, in accordance with Article 28 GDPR and with contracts prepared in collaboration with Iscte's Research Support Office (GAI) and Legal Office (Annex 9B).

- By contrast, *non-personal data*, such as outputs from literature reviews, public datasets, or anonymised metadata related to online content analysis, will be stored and managed separately. These materials will be made available through open access channels, including Iscte–University Institute of Lisbon's institutional repository, in line with open science principles and the European Research Council's guidelines on data sharing.

- This distinction between personal/non-personal data ensures both the protection of vulnerable participants' data and the promotion of research transparency and reproducibility where applicable.
- Signed consent forms, which contain participants' identifying information, will be stored in encrypted files or locked physical cabinets separately from research data. Only the PI and a designated data manager will have access to these forms. Consent forms will be destroyed as soon as they are no longer necessary for documenting consent, and in any case no later than the deletion/complete anonymisation of the corresponding research data or upon a justified request from the data subject.

5.3. International Data Transfers

- When personal data is transferred from or to countries outside the European Economic Area (EEA), appropriate legal safeguards—such as the European Commission's Standard Contractual Clauses (SCCs)—will be implemented to ensure compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).
- All data will be encrypted both in transit and at rest. International transfers will be strictly limited to what is necessary for achieving the research objectives and will not involve any use of data for commercial or exploitative purposes. These transfers reflect the project's core principles of equity, justice, and transparency.
- Whenever Standard Contractual Clauses or other contractual safeguards are required for international data transfers, these instruments will be prepared in close collaboration with Iscte's Research Support Office (GAI) and Legal Office, to ensure full compliance with Article 46 GDPR.

5.4. Data Lifecycle

- All personal data will be securely deleted within two years after the end of the project.
- Participants retain the right to access or request the deletion of their personal data at any stage prior to anonymisation and publication. Once anonymised data has been incorporated into disseminated results (e.g. reports, academic publications), it may no longer be possible to isolate and delete individual contributions.
- A detailed "Data Management Plan", approved and oversighted by the Iscte–University Institute of Lisbon's Data Protection Officer and by the European Research Council will be implemented (available in Annex 12).
- Contact details collected solely for recruitment purposes (e.g. email lists, phone numbers, messages, field notes containing identifiers) will be used only until the recruitment phase for each activity is completed. These data will then be deleted or anonymised without delay and, in any case, no later than the moment when the corresponding research data are anonymised or erased.

In addition to the measures described above, the research team will comply with the technical and organisational measures set out in sections E1 (general technical and organisational safeguards for secure data processing, such as secure storage, access

control and encryption) and E2 (specific security and confidentiality measures for research activities) of Iscte's *Guidelines for Researchers in Scientific Research Activities*.

6. Ethical Approval and Oversight

6.1. Authorisations

- Fieldwork will commence only after formal approval by the Ethics Committee of the School of Sociology and Public Policy (ESPP) at Iscte–University Institute of Lisbon.
- Additional local approvals will be obtained in each country involved in Subproject 4.

6.2. Ethical Guidelines

All research activities will comply with:

- The EU Charter of Fundamental Rights.
- The European Convention on Human Rights.
- The UN Declaration of Human Rights.
- Horizon Europe Ethics Guidelines.
- The EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR – Regulation 2016/679).
- Iscte–University Institute of Lisbon's Data Protection Policy and Code of Ethical Conduct.
- Guidelines for researchers on personal data protection in scientific research at Iscte–University Institute of Lisbon.

The institutional Data Protection Officer will advise the team on legal compliance, particularly with regard to the processing of racial or ethnic data under GDPR Article 9.

7. Informed Consent and Information Sharing

7.1. Participant Information

All participants will receive an information sheet that clearly outlines:

- The purpose, scope, and funding of the project.
- The voluntary nature of participation.
- Data handling and pseudonymisation procedures.
- Contact details for the PI and DPO.
- Their rights to withdraw or request access to personal data.

7.2 Consent Process

- A signed informed consent form will be required before any data is collected. Consent forms will be prepared in duplicate: one copy will be retained by the research team, and the other will be given to the participants for their records.
- Consent will cover agreement to data collection (including audio/video recording where applicable), data use, and the right to withdraw at any point without penalty.
- For online interviews, where obtaining a signed form may not be feasible, oral consent will be obtained and audio-recorded with the participant's permission, in line with approved ethical guidelines.
- For focus groups, participants will be asked to agree to a confidentiality clause as part of the consent process, explicitly committing not to disclose or discuss any information shared during the group session outside of that setting.

7.3 Debriefing and Post-Participation Communication

At the end of each interview, focus group or observational activity, participants will receive a brief debriefing. This will include: (i) a thank-you for their time and contribution; (ii) a short reminder of the overall aims of the *fAIces* project and the specific objectives of the activity in which they took part; and (iii) clarification that no deception or deliberate withholding of information was used in the study design.

The debriefing will also reiterate participants' rights, including the possibility to withdraw their data (where still identifiable), and will provide contact details for the Principal Investigator and the project team in case participants wish to ask questions, share concerns or request a summary of the main findings at a later stage. Where appropriate, participants will be signposted to additional sources of information about facial recognition technologies, as well as to relevant support or community organisations, particularly in Subproject 4.

In line with the benefit-sharing and community engagement strategy described in Section 9, participants will be informed that non-technical summaries and other accessible materials (e.g. short videos, visual summaries) will be made available and that they may request access to these resources or to further information about the project's results.

8. Potential for Misuse and Mitigation Measures

Given the sensitive nature of facial recognition technologies and their public policy implications, the project recognises the risk of misuse or misrepresentation of its findings. To mitigate this:

- **All dissemination materials** will be carefully vetted to avoid sensationalism, stigmatisation, discrimination, or unintended identifiability of individuals/communities (internal review by PI and relevant subproject lead; additional review by local partner where relevant).

- **Unexpected findings procedure + disclosure policy (implemented).** The project applies an “Unexpected Findings Procedure and Disclosure Policy” (Annex 13), overseen by the PI and, where relevant, the Host Institution’s Data Protection Officer/Ethics bodies. In *fAICES*, “unexpected findings” include (non-exhaustive):
 - (i) credible/imminent risk of harm or reprisals;
 - (ii) unanticipated collection/disclosure of unnecessary identifiers or special-category data;
 - (iii) third-party requests for identifiable data/recordings;
 - (iv) unforeseen local legal/ethical constraints affecting fieldwork;
 - (v) any data incident or security breach;
 - (vi) emergent misuse risk in planned dissemination.

Workflow: pause/contain → inform PI → consult DPO/Ethics Committee and/or local partner as applicable → decide mitigation (e.g., redact/exclude data; modify tools/materials/consent; pause dissemination; seek additional local approvals; implement incident response) → document decision and rationale → record in the Unexpected Findings Log → notify ERCEA if protocol amendments or material changes to ethics risks are required.

Disclosure policy (principles): confidentiality by default; minimal and harm-reducing disclosure only on a need-to-know basis; participants are informed when it concerns their rights/safety/consent choices unless doing so creates additional risk; no disclosure of identifiable data to third parties unless required by law and following institutional consultation.

- **Participants’ voices**, especially from vulnerable groups, will be treated with care in public outputs to preserve dignity, accuracy, and context.
- **Documentation and accountability:** all cases and decisions will be logged and reviewed periodically by the PI; advisory board input, where relevant, will be sought in anonymised/aggregated form to avoid unnecessary exposure.

9. Benefit-Sharing and Community Engagement

In Subproject 4, which includes fieldwork with potentially vulnerable communities, the project will implement benefit-sharing and knowledge-return strategies to support ethical reciprocity and social accountability. These measures include:

Co-Produced, Culturally Sensitive Short Videos

In collaboration with local participants and organisations, the research team will develop short video materials summarising key research insights. These videos will be co-scripted

and reviewed with community members to ensure accuracy, relevance, and cultural resonance. They will be made available in appropriate languages and accessible formats for community circulation.

Knowledge-Sharing Sessions

In-person or virtual sessions will be organised with participants, local partners, and intermediaries to discuss preliminary findings, receive feedback, and co-reflect on interpretations. These sessions will serve not only to validate results but also to foster dialogue and future collaboration.

Accessible Return of Findings

A central ethical commitment of Subproject 4 is to ensure that research results are returned to participants and communities in non-technical, accessible, and locally meaningful formats. These may include visual summaries, translated briefs, or interactive discussions, tailored to the cultural and communicative norms of the involved communities.

In cases where participants wish to be identified by name or image in scientific or public outputs, the research team will conduct an additional ethical assessment. This includes discussing with the participant the potential risks (e.g. public exposure, professional or community repercussions) and documenting their informed decision. The PI retains the right to decline identifiable publication if the risks are deemed disproportionate.

These strategies are aligned with the principles of community-based participatory research and aim to empower participants by recognising their role as co-producers of knowledge, rather than merely subjects of study.

10. Ethical Monitoring and Responsibilities

- The Principal Investigator (PI) will oversee the implementation of all ethical safeguards.
- The Host Institution (Associação Iscte Conhecimento e Inovação – Centro de Valorização e Transferência de Tecnologias (CVTT-ISCTE)) bears contractual responsibility for compliance.
- All relevant documentation (consent forms, DPO consultation, local approvals) will be kept on file and made available to ERCEA upon request.

11. Team Roles and Access to Personal Data

The *fAICES* project formally distinguishes between team members and collaborators, as defined in the internal governance document “Team Roles and Access to Personal Data” (document available in Annex 11).

- Team members (researchers employed, contracted, or funded by the project) have access to raw empirical data collected through fieldwork and are bound by confidentiality agreements and institutional codes of conduct.
- Collaborators (contributors not formally employed or funded by the project) do not have access to raw personal data unless a specific agreement is established and approved by the Principal Investigator and, where applicable, the Data Protection Officer.

This role distinction ensures compliance with the principles of purpose limitation, data minimisation, and access control under the GDPR. The list of team members and collaborators is reviewed and updated periodically by the PI and is available on the official website of the project.

Where external service providers (such as translation, transcription or facilitation services) need to handle personal data for the purposes of this project, they will not be considered research collaborators but data processors acting on behalf of Iscte. Their activities will be governed by written data processing agreements or equivalent legal instruments in accordance with Article 28 GDPR, prepared and/or validated with the support of the Research Support Office (GAI) and the Iscte's Legal Office.

12. Addendum: Clarifications on Data Protection Measures (as per DPO guidance)

Following the preliminary review by the institutional Data Protection Officer, the following clarifications and additions are made to reinforce compliance with GDPR and strengthen data protection safeguards within the *fAIces* project:

12.1. Duty of Information in Use of Public Data (e.g., Web Crawling)

In cases where data is collected from publicly accessible online sources (such as websites, blogs, or social media platforms) using automated or semi-automated methods (e.g., web crawling), the *fAIces* project recognises its legal and ethical responsibility to inform data subjects in accordance with Article 14 of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Although the data in question is publicly available, the project acknowledges that its structured collection and processing may still involve personal data, triggering the obligation to ensure transparency.

Accordingly, the project will implement the following measures:

Online Privacy and Ethics Notice

A dedicated Privacy and Ethics Notice will be published on the official project website. It is included in full in Annex 7. This notice will provide clear and accessible information on:

- The types of data being collected
- The purposes of processing
- The legal basis under GDPR
- Data storage and retention practices

- Data subject rights and the procedure for exercising them
- Contact details of the data controller and the institutional Data Protection Officer at Iscte–University Institute of Lisbon.

Justification for Exceptions (Article 14(5)(b) GDPR)

In situations where direct notification of data subjects is deemed impossible or would involve a disproportionate effort—for example, due to the volume or nature of publicly available content—the project will rely on the exception provided in Article 14(5)(b). In such cases, a clear justification framework will be applied, and the rationale for the exemption will be documented and retained for accountability purposes, in line with GDPR requirements and ethical best practices.

Legal and Ethical Framework for Data Collection

- In accordance with Article 3 of Directive (EU) 2019/790 on copyright and related rights in the Digital Single Market, this project engages in webcrawling, and by extension, in text and data mining (TDM) solely for the purposes of scientific research.
- The content to be accessed is publicly available and technical measures to exclude automated access (e.g., robots.txt files) will be respected.
- All data is used strictly for non-commercial, academic analysis and will not be republished or redistributed. Contractual clauses that attempt to restrict such lawful scientific use are not enforceable under Article 7 of the Directive.

Internal Procedures and Training

These procedures will be included in the internal methodological and ethical guidance used by research team members involved in the collection and processing of digital data. All team members will be briefed on these obligations as part of the project’s data protection training. This framework ensures that the use of publicly available data in the *fAices* project is conducted with respect for fundamental rights, transparency, and ethical integrity, in full compliance with European and national data protection regulations.

12.2. International Data Transfers to/from Countries Without Adequacy Decisions

In subprojects where personal data may be collected from or transferred to countries that do not benefit from an adequacy decision by the European Commission, the project commits to:

- Obtaining explicit, informed consent from all data subjects prior to any such transfer.
- Providing a clear explanation of the potential risks associated with international data transfers, including the possibility of reduced legal remedies or data protection safeguards.
- Implementing Standard Contractual Clauses (SCCs) and other appropriate safeguards where applicable. Whenever Standard Contractual Clauses or other contractual safeguards are required for international data transfers, these instruments will be

prepared in close collaboration with Iscte's Research Support Office (GAI) and Legal Office, to ensure full compliance with Article 46 GDPR.

- Where it is not possible to implement Standard Contractual Clauses or other appropriate safeguards under Article 46 GDPR, international transfers will rely on the participant's explicit consent in accordance with Article 49(1)(a) GDPR. In such cases, participants will be clearly informed that the destination country may not offer a level of data protection equivalent to that of the EU and of the potential risks arising from the absence of adequate safeguards.
- Ensuring that participants understand these conditions before data is collected or transferred across jurisdictions.

These requirements apply to both remote participation (e.g., virtual interviews) and any data gathered during in-person fieldwork in such regions.

12.3. Confidentiality Agreements for Non-Employed Team Members and External Service Providers

All members of the research team without a formal contractual link to the host institution (including collaborators, students and visiting researchers) who have access to personal data will be required to sign Iscte's Institutional Confidentiality and Responsibility Term for Researchers/Students (Annex 10) prior to accessing any personal or research data. This agreement:

- sets out the individual's obligation to maintain strict confidentiality;
 - prohibits disclosure or reuse of project data for purposes beyond the fAICES project;
 - establishes individual accountability for data protection compliance and ethical conduct.
- Signed confidentiality and responsibility terms will be stored in a secure, access-restricted location together with the project's ethics documentation.

This measure aims to safeguard participant data and align with institutional and GDPR standards for accountability and security.

Confidentiality and responsibility agreement (Annex 10) do not replace the data processing agreements required under Article 28 GDPR. Whenever third parties process personal data on behalf of Iscte (e.g. transcription companies, external IT providers), a separate data processing contract or equivalent legal instrument will be put in place, prepared in collaboration with Research Support Office (GAI) and Iscte's Legal Office.

Annexes

Annex 1 - Subproject 1

Title of Study: Scientists: Producing Knowledge, Negotiating Power

Annex 1A. Participant Information Sheet

fAIces - Facial Recognition Technologies. Etho-Assemblages and Alternative Futures

(Grant agreement ID: 101140664), funded by the European Research Council

Title of the subproject: Producing Knowledge, Negotiating Power

Principal Investigator: Helena Machado (Helena.Cristina.Machado@iscte-iul.pt), CIES (Centre for Research and Studies in Sociology), Iscte–University Institute of Lisbon

Purpose of the Research

This study explores how scientists working in facial recognition define and apply scientific knowledge in their day-to-day work.

It forms part of the *fAIces* project, funded by the European Research Council, which examines how scientific expertise is shaped—not just by data or methods, but also by institutional settings, collaboration with industry or regulators, decision-making under uncertainty, and responses to ethical or societal concerns.

Our aim is to understand how scientific decisions are made in practice, particularly in fields like facial recognition that involve complex public and policy debates.

You have been invited because you are involved in research or development in facial recognition technologies. We are interested in your experiences and views on how research is conducted, how decisions are made, and how scientific roles and responsibilities are understood in this field.

Voluntary Participation

Your participation is entirely voluntary. You may refuse to answer any question or withdraw from the study at any time without providing a reason and without facing any negative consequences.

What Participation Involves

You will be invited to participate in a semi-structured interview (either in person or online) lasting approximately 60–90 minutes. With your consent, the interview will be audio-recorded for transcription and analysis.

Confidentiality

Your identity will be protected by using a pseudonym in all research outputs. Only the core research team will have access to the data. Results will be presented in such a way that individuals cannot be identified.

Data Handling and Retention

- Your interview will be conducted either face-to-face or online (using a secure video conferencing platform), depending on the context and your preference. In either case, your responses may be audio recorded and transcribed for research purposes.

- Audio recordings will be securely deleted immediately after transcription and verification. Transcripts and other pseudonymised data will be stored on encrypted, offline devices or on secure institutional servers at Iscte–University Institute of Lisbon. Identifiable personal data will not be stored on external commercial cloud services. Data will be stored only on encrypted devices and on institutional servers and licensed cloud services provided by Iscte (for example, Microsoft 365 / Microsoft Teams), which are protected by contractual and technical safeguards.
- The project is based at Associação Iscte Conhecimento e Inovação – Centro de Valorização e Transferência de Tecnologias (Iscte CI), CIES, Iscte–University Institute of Lisbon, in the European Union, and is therefore subject to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Personal data collected during the research, including from interviews conducted outside the EU, may be transferred to and stored in the EU, where it will be protected through strict security measures, including encryption, pseudonymisation, and restricted access. If no equivalent legal safeguards can be put in place, any international transfer of your data will only occur with your explicit consent, after we explain the possible risks to you.
- If the interview is conducted online, we will use secure, institutionally licensed platforms (such as Microsoft Teams), in line with Iscte’s data protection policies.
- All data will be used solely for research purposes. No identifying information will appear in any publications or presentations. Transcripts will be retained for two years after the end of the project and then securely and permanently deleted.

Legal Basis and Your Rights

This study complies with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and local data protection laws in each country involved. You have the right to:

- Access your personal data.
- Request correction or deletion of your data (unless already anonymised and published).
- Withdraw consent at any time.
- Withdrawing your consent will not affect the lawfulness of any data processing that took place before your withdrawal.
- If you consider it necessary, you also have the right to lodge a complaint with the competent Data Protection Authority. In Portugal, this is the Portuguese Data Protection Authority (Comissão Nacional de Proteção de Dados – CNPD).

The data controller for this research is Iscte – University Institute of Lisbon (Iscte – Instituto Universitário de Lisboa). Iscte – Instituto Universitário de Lisboa is responsible for deciding how and why your personal data are processed in this project.

For any doubts, concerns or need of additional information, and for any questions about how your personal data are handled or to exercise your data protection rights (access, rectification, erasure, restriction, objection), please contact the Principal Investigator, Helena Machado (Helena.Cristina.Machado@iscte-iul.pt).

Thank you for reading this information. Please keep this document for your records. The next page contains the consent form.

Annex 1B. Consent Form

fAIces - Facial Recognition Technologies. Etho-Assemblages and Alternative Futures (Grant agreement ID: 101140664), funded by the European Research Council

Title of the subproject: Producing Knowledge, Negotiating Power

Principal Investigator: Helena Machado (Helena.Cristina.Machado@iscte-iul.pt), CIES (Centre for Research and Studies in Sociology), Iscte–University Institute of Lisbon, Portugal

Please read each statement and tick the box to confirm your agreement:

- I confirm that I have read and understood the Participant Information Sheet.
- I have had the opportunity to ask questions and received satisfactory answers.
- I voluntarily agree to participate in this study.
- I consent to the audio recording of the interview.
- I understand that the interview may be conducted either in person or online. If the interview is conducted online, a secure, institutionally licensed video-conferencing platform (such as Microsoft Teams) will be used, in accordance with Iscte’s data protection and security policies. If it takes place outside the European Economic Area (EEA), I consent to the transfer of my data to the EU, under the safeguards described in the Participant Information Sheet.
- I understand that I can withdraw from the study at any time without giving a reason, and without any negative consequences.
- I understand that the data collected will be used solely for academic research purposes, and that my anonymity and confidentiality will be protected.

Future use and open science

- I agree that fully anonymised data from my participation may be shared in open-access research repositories (such as the Iscte community on Zenodo and the Iscte institutional repository) for future scientific use.
- I do not agree that my anonymised data are made publicly available in open-access repositories. My decision will not affect my participation in this study in any way.

Declaration:

I declare that I have read and understood this document, and the information provided to me verbally. I voluntarily agree to participate in this study, in accordance with the terms outlined above. I authorise the use and dissemination of the research results in academic and scientific contexts, with my identity protected and anonymity guaranteed.

Interviewee's name (Printed): _____

Signature: _____

Date: _____

Interviewer's name (Printed): _____

Signature: _____

Date: _____

Annex 1C. Data Collection Instrument (Interview Guide – Scientists)

fAIces - Facial Recognition Technologies. Etho-Assemblages and Alternative Futures (Grant agreement ID: 101140664), funded by the European Research Council

Themes and Sample Questions

1. Scientific Practice and Knowledge-Making

- Can you describe how research in the domain/relate to facial recognition/facial analysis/computer vision (adjust to the interviewee's scientific field) is typically conducted in your team?
- What kinds of data are considered most important in your field? And what kinds of methods are mostly valued?
- How do you evaluate the quality of a given finding?

2. Working with Complexity and Constraints

- Currently, is there any aspect related to facial recognition research that worries you?
- In your experience, what kinds of limitations arise in facial recognition research?
- What were (recent) decisions you made about (researching on) facial recognition? How do you reach those decisions?
- Did you ever deal with things that are hard to measure, predict, or validate? What do you think about it?
- Are there areas where more evidence or tools are still needed? If so, could you please mention the areas that, in your opinion, are the most urgent. Why?

3. Collaborations and Institutional Dynamics

- How does your research relate to broader collaborations — with companies, regulators, or other scientists?
- How would you evaluate your last experience of collaboration in facial recognition research? Looking back, what were the main positive and negative aspects of your experiences of collaboration?
- How does your team approach questions of accountability or responsibility?

4. Publics and Ethics

- What do you think about the public debates around facial recognition? Is there any ethical concern associated with the public debates (e.g., surveillance, fairness) that influence your work? If so, in what way?
- How would you describe the relationship between your research and public interest?
- According to you, you or your team engage or don't engage with stakeholders or the wider public? If not, why not? If so, how do you engaged with stakeholders or the wider public?

Technical and Organisational Safeguards

- **Data Collection:** Interviews will be recorded using encrypted devices (T1 USB or institutional-approved tools).
- **Pseudonymisation:** Names and any identifiable references will be replaced during transcription.

- Access: Only the PI and core research team members have access.
- Transmission: Identifiable personal data will not be stored on external commercial cloud services. Data will be stored only on encrypted devices and on institutional servers and licensed cloud services provided by Iscte (for example, Microsoft 365 / Microsoft Teams), which are protected by contractual and technical safeguards. Data will be transferred only via encrypted USB devices.
- Retention and Deletion: Data will be stored for up to two years after the end of the project, then securely deleted.

Annex 2 - Subproject 2

Title of Study: Start-Ups and Tech Companies: Turning Code into Products

Annex 2A. Participant Information Sheet

fAICES - Facial Recognition Technologies. Etho-Assemblages and Alternative Futures (Grant agreement ID: 101140664), funded by the European Research Council

Title of the subproject: Start-Ups and Tech Companies: Turning Code Into Products

Principal Investigator: Helena Machado (Helena.Cristina.Machado@iscte-iul.pt), CIES (Centre for Research and Studies in Sociology), Iscte–University Institute of Lisbon, Portugal

Purpose of the Research

This study explores how professionals working in facial recognition technologies—particularly within start-ups and companies—develop, position, and apply their work in everyday contexts. It forms part of the *fAICES* project, funded by the European Research Council, which examines how technological expertise is shaped—not just by technical development, but also by organisational settings, interactions with regulators or clients, decision-making under uncertainty, and responses to ethical, legal, or societal concerns. Our aim is to understand how innovation happens in practice, especially in fields like facial recognition that raise complex questions in public, commercial, and policy domains. You have been invited because you are involved in the development or deployment of facial recognition technologies. We are interested in your experiences and views on how decisions are made, how technologies are shaped, and how responsibilities are understood in this field.

Voluntary Participation

Your participation is entirely voluntary. You may refuse to answer any question or withdraw from the study at any time without providing a reason and without facing any negative consequences.

What Participation Involves

You will be invited to participate in a semi-structured interview (either in person or online) lasting approximately 60–90 minutes. With your consent, the interview will be audio-recorded for transcription and analysis.

Confidentiality

Your identity will be protected by using a pseudonym in all research outputs. Only the core research team will have access to the data. Results will be presented in such a way that individuals cannot be identified.

Data Handling and Retention

- Your interview will be conducted either face-to-face or online (using a secure video conferencing platform), depending on the context and your preference. In either case, your responses may be audio recorded and transcribed for research purposes.

- Audio recordings will be securely deleted immediately after transcription and verification. Transcripts and other pseudonymised data will be stored on encrypted, offline devices or on secure institutional servers at Iscte–University Institute of Lisbon. Identifiable personal data will not be stored on external commercial cloud services. Data will be stored only on encrypted devices and on institutional servers and licensed cloud services provided by Iscte (for example, Microsoft 365 / Microsoft Teams), which are protected by contractual and technical safeguards.
- The project is based at Associação Iscte Conhecimento e Inovação – Centro de Valorização e Transferência de Tecnologias (Iscte CI), CIES, Iscte–University Institute of Lisbon, in the European Union, and is therefore subject to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Personal data collected during the research, including from interviews conducted outside the EU, may be transferred to and stored in the EU, where it will be protected through strict security measures, including encryption, pseudonymisation, and restricted access. If no equivalent legal safeguards can be put in place, any international transfer of your data will only occur with your explicit consent, after we explain the possible risks to you.
- If the interview is conducted online, we will use secure, institutionally licensed platforms (such as Microsoft Teams), in line with Iscte’s data protection policies.
- .- All data will be used solely for research purposes. No identifying information will appear in any publications or presentations. Transcripts will be retained for two years after the end of the project and then securely and permanently deleted.

Legal Basis and Your Rights

This study complies with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and local data protection laws in each country involved. You have the right to:

- Access your personal data.
- Request correction or deletion of your data (unless already anonymised and published).
- Withdraw consent at any time.
- Withdrawing your consent will not affect the lawfulness of any data processing that took place before your withdrawal.
- If you consider it necessary, you also have the right to lodge a complaint with the competent Data Protection Authority. In Portugal, this is the Portuguese Data Protection Authority (Comissão Nacional de Proteção de Dados – CNPD).

The data controller for this research is Iscte – University Institute of Lisbon (Iscte – Instituto Universitário de Lisboa). Iscte – Instituto Universitário de Lisboa is responsible for deciding how and why your personal data are processed in this project.

For any doubts, concerns or need of additional information, and for any questions about how your personal data are handled or to exercise your data protection rights (access, rectification, erasure, restriction, objection), please contact the Principal Investigator, Helena Machado (Helena.Cristina.Machado@iscte-iul.pt).

Thank you for reading this information. Please keep this document for your records. The next page contains the consent form.

Annex 2B. Consent Form

fAIces - Facial Recognition Technologies. Etho-Assemblages and Alternative Futures (Grant agreement ID: 101140664), funded by the European Research Council

Title of the subproject: Start-Ups and Tech Companies: Turning Code into Products

Principal Investigator: Helena Machado (Helena.Cristina.Machado@iscte-iul.pt), CIES (Centre for Research and Studies in Sociology), Iscte–University Institute of Lisbon, Portugal

Please read each statement and tick the box to confirm your agreement:

- I confirm that I have read and understood the Participant Information Sheet.
- I have had the opportunity to ask questions and received satisfactory answers.
- I voluntarily agree to participate in this study.
- I consent to the audio recording of the interview.
- I understand that the interview may be conducted either in person or online. If the interview is conducted online, a secure, institutionally licensed video-conferencing platform (such as Microsoft Teams) will be used, in accordance with Iscte’s data protection and security policies. If it takes place outside the European Economic Area (EEA), I consent to the transfer of my data to the EU, under the safeguards described in the Participant Information Sheet.
- I understand that I can withdraw from the study at any time without giving a reason, and without any negative consequences.
- I understand that the data collected will be used solely for academic research purposes, and that my anonymity and confidentiality will be protected.

Future use and open science

- I agree that fully anonymised data from my participation may be shared in open-access research repositories (such as the Iscte community on Zenodo and the Iscte institutional repository) for future scientific use.
- I do not agree that my anonymised data are made publicly available in open-access repositories. My decision will not affect my participation in this study in any way.

Declaration:

I declare that I have read and understood this document, and the information provided to me verbally. I voluntarily agree to participate in this study, in accordance with the terms outlined above. I authorise the use and dissemination of the research results in academic and scientific contexts, with my identity protected and anonymity guaranteed.

Interviewee's name (Printed): _____

Signature: _____

Date: _____

Interviewer's name (Printed): _____

Signature: _____

Date: _____

Annex 2C. Data Collection Instrument (Interview Guide – Start-Up Professionals)
fAIces - Facial Recognition Technologies. Etho-Assemblages and Alternative Futures
(Grant agreement ID: 101140664), funded by the European Research Council

Themes and Sample Questions

1. Innovation and Legitimacy

- How do you define “innovation” in the Artificial Intelligence/Facial recognition technologies (adjust to the interviewee’s professional practices) domain?
- What kinds of external scrutiny have you faced when developing or deploying facial recognition technologies?
- What were (recent) challenges you dealt with to legitimate your work on facial recognition technologies? How did you deal with such challenges?

2. Ethical Practices

- Currently, is there any aspect related to facial recognition technologies that worries you? Why?
- Are there internal discussions or mechanisms for addressing ethical issues? If not, why not? If so, could you please mention the mechanisms that, in your opinion, are the most adequate. Why?
- Did you ever engage with debates around surveillance, bias, or fairness? If not, why not? If so, how did you engage with such debates?

3. Navigating Controversies

- In your professional experience, have you encountered public backlash? What do you think about it?
- How does your work relate to regulatory scrutiny?
- How would you describe the strategies used internally to mitigate risks or controversies? Looking back, what were the main positive and negative aspects of such strategies?

4. Start-Up Identity

- How do start-up dynamics influence your ability to implement ethical safeguards?
- What were (recent) technical and governance decisions you made about (working) with facial recognition technologies? How do you reach such decisions? How would you evaluate the role of resource limitations in such processes?

Technical and Organisational Safeguards

- Data Collection: Interviews conducted via encrypted software (e.g., Teams with E2E encryption, or institutional equipment).
- Pseudonymisation: Personal identifiers (e.g., company name, job title) are replaced with anonymised codes during transcription.
- Access: Only the PI and core research team members have access.

- Storage: Data stored in an encrypted local directory, no cloud syncing, following Iscte–University Institute of Lisbon 's data protection policy.
- Confidentiality: Team members signed confidentiality agreements; access to data is role-specific.
- Retention and Deletion: All data will be securely destroyed within two years post-project.

Annex 3 - Subproject 3

Title of Study: Advocacy and Activism: Voices of Resistance

Annex 3A. Participant Information Sheet

fAICES - Facial Recognition Technologies. Etho-Assemblages and Alternative Futures
(Grant agreement ID: 101140664), funded by the European Research Council

Title of the subproject: Advocacy and Activism: Voices of Resistance

Principal Investigator: Helena Machado (Helena.Cristina.Machado@iscte-iul.pt), CIES (Centre for Research and Studies in Sociology), Iscte–University Institute of Lisbon, Portugal

Purpose of the Research

This study explores how advocacy groups, civil society organisations, and activists engage with facial recognition technologies as political and ethical issues.

It forms part of the *fAICES* project, funded by the European Research Council, which examines how technological expertise and authority are shaped—not only through technical development, but also through contestation, public debate, and alternative visions of what technologies should (or should not) do.

Our aim is to understand how resistance, critique, and advocacy emerge in practice—particularly in relation to facial recognition technologies, which have become a focus of intense public, legal, and ethical debate.

You have been invited because of your involvement in activism, campaigning, or advocacy related to facial recognition or broader issues of surveillance, technology, and social justice. We are interested in your perspectives, strategies, and visions for how technologies are challenged, resisted, or reimagined in this field.

Voluntary Participation

Your participation is entirely voluntary. You may refuse to answer any question or withdraw from the study at any time without providing a reason and without facing any negative consequences.

What Participation Involves

You will be invited to participate in a semi-structured interview (either in person or online) lasting approximately 60–90 minutes. With your consent, the interview will be audio-recorded for transcription and analysis.

Confidentiality

Your identity will be protected by using a pseudonym in all research outputs. Only the core research team will have access to the data. Results will be presented in such a way that individuals cannot be identified.

Data Handling and Retention

- Your interview will be conducted either face-to-face or online (using a secure video conferencing platform), depending on the context and your preference. In either case, your responses may be audio recorded and transcribed for research purposes.

- Audio recordings will be securely deleted immediately after transcription and verification. Transcripts and other pseudonymised data will be stored on encrypted, offline devices or on secure institutional servers at Iscte–University Institute of Lisbon’s CVTT. Identifiable personal data will not be stored on external commercial cloud services. Data will be stored only on encrypted devices and on institutional servers and licensed cloud services provided by Iscte (for example, Microsoft 365 / Microsoft Teams), which are protected by contractual and technical safeguards.
 - The project is based at Associação Iscte Conhecimento e Inovação – Centro de Valorização e Transferência de Tecnologias (Iscte CI), CIES, Iscte–University Institute of Lisbon, in the European Union, and is therefore subject to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Personal data collected during the research, including from interviews conducted outside the EU, may be transferred to and stored in the EU, where it will be protected through strict security measures, including encryption, pseudonymisation, and restricted access. If no equivalent legal safeguards can be put in place, any international transfer of your data will only occur with your explicit consent, after we explain the possible risks to you.
 - If the interview is conducted online, we will use secure, institutionally licensed platforms (such as Microsoft Teams), in line with Iscte’s data protection policies.
- All data will be used solely for research purposes. No identifying information will appear in any publications or presentations. Transcripts will be retained for two years after the end of the project and then securely and permanently deleted.

Legal Basis and Your Rights

This study complies with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and local data protection laws in each country involved. You have the right to:

- Access your personal data.
- Request correction or deletion of your data (unless already anonymised and published).
- Withdraw consent at any time.
- Withdrawing your consent will not affect the lawfulness of any data processing that took place before your withdrawal.
- If you consider it necessary, you also have the right to lodge a complaint with the competent Data Protection Authority. In Portugal, this is the Portuguese Data Protection Authority (Comissão Nacional de Proteção de Dados – CNPD).

The data controller for this research is Iscte – University Institute of Lisbon (Iscte – Instituto Universitário de Lisboa). Iscte – Instituto Universitário de Lisboa is responsible for deciding how and why your personal data are processed in this project.

For any doubts, concerns or need of additional information, and for any questions about how your personal data are handled or to exercise your data protection rights (access, rectification, erasure, restriction, objection), please contact the Principal Investigator, Helena Machado (Helena.Cristina.Machado@iscte-iul.pt).

Thank you for reading this information. Please keep this document for your records. The next page contains the consent form.

Annex 3B. Consent Form

fAIces - Facial Recognition Technologies. Etho-Assemblages and Alternative Futures (Grant agreement ID: 101140664), funded by the European Research Council

Title of the subproject: Advocacy and Activism: Voices of Resistance

Principal Investigator: Helena Machado (Helena.Cristina.Machado@iscte-iul.pt), CIES (Centre for Research and Studies in Sociology), Iscte–University Institute of Lisbon, Portugal

Please read each statement and tick the box to confirm your agreement:

- I confirm that I have read and understood the Participant Information Sheet.
- I have had the opportunity to ask questions and received satisfactory answers.
- I voluntarily agree to participate in this study.
- I consent to the audio recording of the interview.
- I understand that the interview may be conducted either in person or online. If the interview is conducted online, a secure, institutionally licensed video-conferencing platform (such as Microsoft Teams) will be used, in accordance with Iscte’s data protection and security policies. If it takes place outside the European Economic Area (EEA), I consent to the transfer of my data to the EU, under the safeguards described in the Participant Information Sheet.
- I understand that I can withdraw from the study at any time without giving a reason, and without any negative consequences.
- I understand that the data collected will be used solely for academic research purposes, and that my anonymity and confidentiality will be protected.

Future use and open science

- I agree that fully anonymised data from my participation may be shared in open-access research repositories (such as the Iscte community on Zenodo and the Iscte institutional repository) for future scientific use.
- I do not agree that my anonymised data are made publicly available in open-access repositories. My decision will not affect my participation in this study in any way.

Declaration:

I declare that I have read and understood this document, and the information provided to me verbally. I voluntarily agree to participate in this study, in accordance with the terms outlined above. I authorise the use and dissemination of the research results in academic and scientific contexts, with my identity protected and anonymity guaranteed.

Interviewee's name (Printed): _____

Signature: _____

Date: _____

Interviewer's name (Printed): _____

Signature: _____

Date: _____

Annex 3C. Data Collection Instrument (Interview Guide – Advocacy Groups / Activists)

fAIces - Facial Recognition Technologies. Etho-Assemblages and Alternative Futures (Grant agreement ID: 101140664), funded by the European Research Council

Themes and Sample Questions

1. Controversies and Publics

- What do you think about the controversies around facial recognition technologies? How would you describe your involvement with such controversies?
- How do you see power relations at play in the promotion and deployment of facial recognition technologies?

2. Politics of Resistance

- How does your organisation engage with facial recognition technologies?
- Have you ever developed forms of resistance or critique around facial recognition technologies? Please, tell us what you remember about it.
- Could you please mention the forms of resistance or critique that, in your opinion, are the most adequate. Why?

3. Activist Infrastructure

- How do you coordinate your actions (locally, transnationally)?
- How would you evaluate your last experience of coordinating an action related to facial recognition technologies?
- Looking back, what were the main positive and negative aspects of your experiences of activism? What risks or ethical dilemmas arise from your activism?

4. Knowledge and Counter-Narratives

- What kinds of evidence, knowledge, or discourse do you mobilise to resist or critique facial recognition technologies? Why?
- According to you, you or your organisation engage or don't engage with scientists, policymakers, or artists? If not, why not? If so, in what way?

Technical and Organisational Safeguards

- Sensitivity Acknowledgment: Participants may be at legal, social, or reputational risk. Great care will be taken to protect identity where desired.
- Consent Options: Participants may opt for pseudonymity or choose to be identified by name (if publicly active).
- Secure Recording: Conducted via encrypted devices; no live transcripts shared with external platforms.
- Storage: Encrypted, offline storage. Access limited to PI and PhD 3 only.
- Ethical Review: Any use of direct quotes or identifiable narratives will be reconfirmed with the participant before dissemination.

Annex 4 - Subproject 4

Title of Study: Black Communities: Experiences of Surveillance and Resistance

Annex 4A. Outline for Local Ethical Support

Project Title

fAlces – Facial Recognition Technologies: Etho-Assemblages and Alternative Futures
(European Research Council Advanced Grant No. 101140664)

Subproject 4 Focus

Exploring the experiences of Black communities in [COUNTRY NAME] in relation to facial recognition technologies, their social impacts, and community-led interpretations, practices, and resistance.

Coordinating Institution and Ethics Approval

This subproject is led by Associação Iscte Conhecimento e Inovação – Centro de Valorização e Transferência de Tecnologias (Iscte CI), CIES, Iscte–University Institute of Lisbon, Portugal, with full ethics approval granted by the coordinating institution’s ethics committee.

ERC-funded research requires that local institutions and/or community partners in countries where fieldwork is conducted be informed of the research and provide support or acknowledgment in accordance with local norms.

Purpose of Local Ethics Support

To confirm that the planned research activities in [CITY, COUNTRY]—specifically focus groups and co-produced video interviews with members of Black communities—are conducted ethically and respectfully, in alignment with local research standards and community practices.

Research Activities in [CITY, COUNTRY]

- Focus groups with voluntary adult participants from Black communities.
- Optional co-produced video interviews (with informed, recorded consent).
- Conducted with trained co-facilitators, including members of local community organisations.
- All participants will receive written and verbal information and will provide explicit, informed consent.
- The study does not process biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying participants (GDPR Article 9). A separate optional co-produced video activity may include recording of image/voice with explicit consent; such recordings are used only for the agreed dissemination purposes and are not used for identification, authentication, or facial recognition.
- Pseudonymisation and secure data handling will be applied according to EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) standards (and local law where applicable).

Main Ethical Considerations

- Voluntary participation and right to withdraw at any time.
- Protection of confidentiality and personal data.
- Cultural and linguistic sensitivity in facilitation and materials.
- Support mechanisms available for emotional distress.

- Return of results in accessible formats to participants and communities.
- Non-extractive, community-accountable research practice.

Requested Local Support

We respectfully request one or more of the following from your institution or organisation:

- A short letter confirming that you are informed of and supportive of this project being carried out in [CITY, COUNTRY].
- Optional: a brief review or comment on our 2-page ethics summary and consent materials (available upon request).
- No legal or binding responsibility is requested — only acknowledgment that the research is ethically aligned with good practices in [COUNTRY].

Annex 4B. Participant Information Sheet (Focus group)

fAICES – Facial Recognition Technologies: Etho-Assemblages and Alternative Futures (Grant agreement ID: 101140664), funded by the European Research Council

Title of Subproject: Black Communities: Experiences of Surveillance and Resistance

Principal Investigator: Helena Machado (Helena.Cristina.Machado@iscte-iul.pt), CIES (Centre for Research and Studies in Sociology), Iscte–University Institute of Lisbon, Portugal

Purpose of the Research

You are invited to take part in a research study exploring how Black communities experience and respond to facial recognition technologies. This project seeks to understand both historical and present-day patterns of racial surveillance, as well as the everyday strategies individuals and communities use to question, resist, or reshape these technologies. It forms part of the *fAICES* project, funded by the European Research Council (Grant No. 101140664).

This research values lived experience, collective knowledge, and the ways Black communities critically engage with technology. You have been invited because of your lived experience, insights, and community knowledge related to how facial recognition and similar technologies impact Black individuals and communities. We believe that these perspectives are essential to understanding how such technologies are felt, interpreted, challenged, and reimaged in everyday life.

Voluntary Participation

Participation is entirely voluntary. You may decline to answer questions or withdraw at any point without explanation or consequences. The researchers will respect your comfort, dignity, and boundaries at all times.

What Participation Involves

You will be invited to participate in a focus group (approximately 90–120 minutes) facilitated by trained researchers and community partners. With your consent, the discussion may be audio-recorded. All questions are optional, and you are free to leave at any time.

Data Handling and Retention

- Any information you share will be kept confidential.
- You may choose to remain anonymous. Data will be pseudonymised and stored securely. It will only be accessed by the Principal Investigator and core research team (including community co-facilitators), all of whom are bound by confidentiality agreements. No data will be shared with third parties or used beyond this project.
- Audio recordings will be securely deleted immediately after transcription and verification. Transcripts and pseudonymised data will be stored on encrypted, offline

devices or secure institutional servers at Iscte–University Institute of Lisbon. Identifiable personal data will not be stored on external commercial cloud services. Data will be stored only on encrypted devices and on institutional servers and licensed cloud services provided by Iscte (for example, Microsoft 365 / Microsoft Teams), which are protected by contractual and technical safeguards.

- Transcripts will be retained for two years after the completion of the project and then securely and permanently deleted.

- For focus groups conducted outside the European Union, any personal data collected (such as transcripts) will be securely transferred to and stored at Iscte–University Institute of Lisbon, in Portugal. These international data transfers will be protected by technical and legal safeguards, in compliance with the European Union General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and relevant local laws. If no equivalent legal safeguards can be put in place, any international transfer of your data will only occur with your explicit consent, after we explain the possible risks to you.

- No identifying data will be shared with third parties, and all data will be used strictly for research purposes.

Sensitive Data Notice

Some aspects of this research may involve topics such as racial identity or discrimination. These will only be discussed if you are comfortable doing so, and your explicit consent will be sought before collecting any sensitive data.

Support Measure

If any part of the conversation causes distress, support options will be made available locally or online.

Legal Basis and Your Rights

This research is conducted in accordance with the European Union General Data Protection Regulation (EU GDPR – Regulation 2016/679) and the United Kingdom General Data Protection Regulation (UK GDPR). For activities taking place in Canada, the United States, and Brazil, we will comply with relevant national or regional data protection laws, such as Personal Information Protection and Electronic Documents Act, SC 2000, c 5 - PIPEDA (Canada), Lei Geral de Proteção de Dados - LGPD (Brazil), and applicable state or federal laws in the United States. You have the right to:

- Access your personal data.
- Request correction or deletion of your data (unless already anonymised and published).
- Withdraw consent at any time.
- Withdrawing your consent will not affect the lawfulness of any data processing that took place before your withdrawal.
- If you consider it necessary, you also have the right to lodge a complaint with the competent Data Protection Authority. In Portugal, this is the Portuguese Data Protection Authority (Comissão Nacional de Proteção de Dados – CNPD).

The data controller for this research is Iscte – University Institute of Lisbon (Iscte – Instituto Universitário de Lisboa). Iscte – Instituto Universitário de Lisboa is responsible for deciding how and why your personal data are processed in this project.

For any doubts, concerns or need of additional information, and for any questions about how your personal data are handled or to exercise your data protection rights (access, rectification, erasure, restriction, objection), please contact the Principal Investigator, Helena Machado (Helena.Cristina.Machado@iscte-iul.pt).

Thank you for reading this information. Please keep this document for your records. The next page contains the consent form.

Annex 4C. Consent Form (Focus group)

fAICES – Facial Recognition Technologies. Etho-Assemblages and Alternative Futures (Grant agreement ID: 101140664), funded by the European Research Council

Title of Subproject: Black Communities: Experiences of Surveillance and Resistance

Principal Investigator: Helena Machado (Helena.Cristina.Machado@iscte-iul.pt), CIES (Centre for Research and Studies in Sociology), Iscte–University Institute of Lisbon, Portugal

Please read each statement and tick the box to confirm your agreement:

- I confirm that I have read and understood the Participant Information Sheet.
- I have had the opportunity to ask questions and received satisfactory answers.
- I voluntarily agree to participate in this focus group.
- I explicitly consent to the processing of information that may reveal my racial or ethnic origin (special category data under GDPR Article 9) for the purposes of this research, as explained in the Participant Information Sheet.
- I consent to the audio recording of the focus group discussion.
- I understand that my data may be transferred to and stored in the European Union (EU), even if the focus group takes place outside the EU, and that this transfer will be protected by legal safeguards as explained in the information sheet.
- I understand that I can withdraw at any time without giving a reason.
- I understand that the data collected will be used solely for academic research, and that my anonymity and confidentiality will be protected.

Future use and open science

- I agree that fully anonymised data from my participation may be shared in open-access research repositories (such as the Iscte community on Zenodo and the Iscte institutional repository) for future scientific use.
- I do not agree that my anonymised data are made publicly available in open-access repositories. My decision will not affect my participation in this study in any way.

Declaration:

I declare that I have read and understood this document, as well as the verbal information provided to me. I freely agree to participate in this study according to the items indicated above, trusting that the information will be used solely for this research and in accordance with the confidentiality assured to me by the researcher. I also authorise the dissemination of the results in scientific contexts, with my anonymity guaranteed.

Interviewee's name (Printed): _____

Signature: _____

Date: _____

Interviewer's name (Printed): _____

Signature: _____

Date: _____

Annex 4D. Focus Group Interview Guide (Black Communities)

fAIces – Facial Recognition Technologies. Etho-Assemblages and Alternative Futures
(Grant agreement ID: 101140664), funded by the European Research Council

Themes and Sample Questions

Opening

- Welcome, introductions, ground rules (respect, confidentiality, all voices matter).
- Icebreaker: When you think about cameras or surveillance in daily life, what's the first word or image that comes to mind?

1. Experiences with Surveillance and Technology

- When did you first hear about facial recognition? What were the circumstances?
- Who here has encountered it personally — at airports, shops, or in the community? What was that like?

Facilitator (group probe): Do others relate to that experience, or was it different for you?

- How do people in your community generally feel about these technologies — safer, more watched, indifferent?
- What about information and safeguards — how do you think people learn (or not learn) about privacy protections?

2. Histories of Racialisation

- Surveillance of Black communities is not new. In your opinion, what forms of surveillance have historically affected your community?
- Do you see connections between those past forms and today's facial recognition technologies?

Group probe: Encourage participants to compare and build on each other's answers.

3. Resistance and Empowerment

- Are there any actions, organisations, or stories that inspire you to resist or critique facial recognition technologies? What do you think about it?
- When you think about empowerment, what does that mean in this context?
- In your opinion, people from your community are expected to participate or not participate in decision making about facial recognition technologies? Why?

Facilitator (group probe): Do you think change is possible, or are these technologies fundamentally harmful?

4. Imagining Alternatives

- If you could reshape or redesign these technologies, what would you want to see change?"

How should decision-makers or tech companies involve your community?

Facilitator (Group probe): Do you think change is possible, or are these technologies fundamentally harmful?

Facilitation Notes

- **Co-facilitation:** Whenever possible, co-facilitate with trusted community members to increase comfort and cultural relevance.
- **Cultural & linguistic adaptation:** Ensure questions, examples, and language reflect participants' context and identity.
- **Ground rules for respectful dialogue:** Establish at the start (confidentiality, no judgment, listen fully, all voices matter).
- **Encourage group interaction:** Use *group probes* (e.g., "Who else feels that way?" "Does anyone see it differently?") to spark conversation across participants, not just with the facilitator.
- **Balance voices:** Invite quieter participants to share; gently manage dominant voices.
- **Probing for depth:** Ask follow-ups like "*Can you give an example?*" or "*Can you tell me more about that?*" to deepen insights.
- **Space for emotion:** Acknowledge that surveillance and discrimination can be sensitive and personal. Allow time for participants to process.
- **Closing and debrief:** End with a reflective, future-oriented question; leave time for informal conversation afterward, so participants don't leave "on the spot."

Technical and Organisational Safeguards

- **Access Control:** Only the PI and core team members, and local co-facilitators (if applicable) will have access to recordings or transcripts.
- **Cultural Sensitivity:** All materials will be pre-tested for cultural appropriateness and co-designed with local partners.
- **Voluntary Disclosure:** No racial or ethnic data will be collected unless directly relevant and based on explicit, informed consent.
- **Anonymisation:** Focus group participants will be assigned pseudonyms; identifying details will be excluded from transcripts.
- **Psychosocial Support:** Where appropriate, local resources or online mental health support services will be identified and shared.
- **Storage:** All data will be encrypted and stored offline or on secure institutional servers. Identifiable personal data will not be stored on external commercial cloud services. Data will be stored only on encrypted devices and on institutional servers and licensed cloud services provided by Iscte (for example, Microsoft 365 / Microsoft Teams), which are protected by contractual and technical safeguards. Audio recordings will be permanently deleted immediately after accurate transcription and quality checks. Transcriptions and other anonymised data will

be securely stored for a period of two years following the conclusion of the project, after which they will be irreversibly deleted.

- All participants will be required to sign a confidentiality agreement as part of the consent process, committing not to disclose, reproduce, or discuss any of the content shared during the group session outside that setting. This is essential to protect the privacy and safety of all participants.
- Field Approval: Local ethics approval will be secured in each country before any focus group is conducted.

Annex 4E. Participant Information Sheet (Videos)

fAIces – Facial Recognition Technologies. Etho-Assemblages and Alternative Futures
(Grant agreement ID: 101140664), funded by the European Research Council

Title of Subproject: Black Communities: Experiences of Surveillance and Resistance

Principal Investigator: Helena Machado (Helena.Cristina.Machado@iscte-iul.pt), CIES (Centre for Research and Studies in Sociology), Iscte–University Institute of Lisbon, Portugal

Invitation to Participate

We are inviting you to take part in a short video that we are creating *together* as part of the *fAIces* project. This research explores how facial recognition technologies are affecting people and communities—especially Black communities—and how people are responding in everyday life.

This video is a way to reflect and share key messages from the project in your own words. It may include your voice, image, or personal reflections—only if and how you feel comfortable. You will have a say in what is shared, and how.

Purpose of the Video

The video is meant to open up conversation and share insights with the wider community—including other participants, local groups, educators, and the general public. It may be shown at events, in educational spaces, or on our website and social media, with your consent.

We want this to be a collaborative and respectful process. Your contribution is entirely voluntary, and you can choose how you would like to be involved.

Voluntary Participation and Use of Recordings

- Your participation is completely voluntary. The video may include recordings of your image and voice. You will be consulted about your contribution and will have the opportunity to review and suggest changes before final publication.

- You may withdraw your consent at any time before the video is published. After publication, withdrawal may not be fully possible, particularly if the video has been downloaded or shared externally. We will, however, make reasonable efforts to respond to any such requests, such as removing the video or specific segments of your contribution from our own channels or preventing further sharing where feasible.

Special category data (GDPR Article 9)

Because this is a video activity, the recording may reveal special category data, including information related to racial or ethnic origin (and potentially other sensitive characteristics). We will only process this type of data with your explicit consent, solely for the purposes described in this information sheet. You may take part in the study without participating in the video component, and you may also choose less identifiable options (e.g., voice only, off-camera, or anonymised comments).

Data Handling and Storage

- All video footage will be securely stored by the research team. It will be shared only with collaborators involved in editing and dissemination. The final edited video may be publicly accessible, unless you request otherwise.
- If the video is recorded outside the European Union, the footage will be securely transferred to and stored in the EU at Associação Iscte Conhecimento e Inovação – Centro de Valorização e Transferência de Tecnologias (Iscte CI), CIES, Iscte–University Institute of Lisbon (Portugal). These international transfers will be protected by appropriate safeguards, in line with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and other applicable data protection laws. If no equivalent legal safeguards can be put in place, any international transfer of your data will only occur with your explicit consent, after we explain the possible risks to you.
- All raw footage will be retained for two years after the project ends. After this period, the raw footage will be securely deleted.

Legal Basis and Your Rights

This research is conducted in accordance with the European Union General Data Protection Regulation (EU GDPR – Regulation 2016/679) and the United Kingdom General Data Protection Regulation (UK GDPR). For activities taking place in Canada, the United States, and Brazil, we will comply with relevant national or regional data protection laws, such as Personal Information Protection and Electronic Documents Act, SC 2000, c 5 - PIPEDA (Canada), Lei Geral de Proteção de Dados - LGPD (Brazil), and applicable state or federal laws in the United States. You have the right to:

- Access or correct your personal data.
- Request deletion before the video is finalised.
- Withdraw your consent any time prior to public release.
- Withdrawing your consent will not affect the lawfulness of any data processing that took place before your withdrawal.
- If you choose to appear with your real name or recognisable image, the research team will discuss with you any potential risks and make sure that your decision is fully informed and voluntary.

You may:

- Decline to answer any questions.
- Pause or stop the recording at any point.
- Choose to appear off-camera while still sharing your voice or insights.
- Request anonymity.

The data controller for this research is Iscte – University Institute of Lisbon (Iscte – Instituto Universitário de Lisboa). Iscte – Instituto Universitário de Lisboa is responsible for deciding how and why your personal data are processed in this project.

For any doubts, concerns or need of additional information, and for any questions about how your personal data are handled or to exercise your data protection rights (access, rectification, erasure, restriction, objection), please contact the Principal Investigator, Helena Machado (Helena.Cristina.Machado@iscte-iul.pt).

Thank you for reading this information. Please keep this document for your records. The next page contains the consent form.

Annex 4F. Consent Form (Videos)

fAIces – Facial Recognition Technologies. Etho-Assemblages and Alternative Futures
(Grant agreement ID: 101140664), funded by the European Research Council

Title of Subproject: Black Communities: Experiences of Surveillance and Resistance

Principal Investigator: Helena Machado (Helena.Cristina.Machado@iscte-iul.pt), CIES (Centre for Research and Studies in Sociology), Iscte–University Institute of Lisbon, Portugal

Please read each statement and tick the box to confirm your agreement:

- I agree to participate in the video production as part of the *fAIces* research project.
- I consent to the use of my image and voice in the recorded material.
- I explicitly consent to the processing of video/audio data that may reveal my racial or ethnic origin (special category data under GDPR Article 9), for the purposes described in the Participant Information Sheet.
- I understand how the video may be edited, published, and shared on public platforms.
- I understand that I can request edits or deletion before publication, but may not be able to withdraw my contribution after public release.
- I understand that my data, including video footage, may be transferred to the EU (Portugal) for secure storage and processing under GDPR-compliant safeguards.

I prefer the following option for how I appear in the final video (choose only one option):

- Show my face and use my full name
- Show my face but do not use my name
- Use my voice only (off-camera)
- Use anonymised comments (no image or recognisable voice; voice alteration if requested)

If you choose to appear with your real name or recognisable image, the research team will discuss with you any potential risks and make sure that your decision is fully informed and voluntary.

Future use and open science

- I agree that fully anonymised data from my participation may be shared in open-access research repositories (such as the Iscte community on Zenodo and the Iscte institutional repository) for future scientific use.
- I do not agree that my anonymised data are made publicly available in open-access repositories. My decision will not affect my participation in this study in any way.

Declaration

I declare that I have read and understood this document, and the information provided to me verbally. I voluntarily agree to participate in this study, in accordance with the terms outlined above. I authorise the use and dissemination of the research results in academic and scientific contexts, with my identity protected and anonymity guaranteed.

Name (Printed): _____

Signature: _____

Date: _____

Annex 4G. Video Interview Guide (Black Communities)

fAIces – Facial Recognition Technologies. Etho-Assemblages and Alternative Futures (Grant agreement ID: 101140664), funded by the European Research Council

This guide outlines the key themes to be explored in short, co-produced video interviews with community participants. The interviews are open-ended and conversational, aiming to reflect participant perspectives, lived experiences, and interpretations of the research findings.

Themes and Possible Prompts

- What do you think about your participation in this research?
- What stood out to you or felt important about the findings?
- What would you want others to learn or understand from this research?
- What does facial recognition mean to you in your daily life?
- What do you expect regarding the future of facial recognition technologies? Is there any aspect that worries you?
- How do you see the role of your community in resisting or rethinking the facial recognition technologies?
- Do you see any connection between this topic and other social issues facing your community?

Participants are warmly encouraged to bring their own stories, concerns, and ideas into the conversation. This is a shared exchange, not a one-way interview. You are free to pause, edit, or shape the recording at any point, and you can decide what you are comfortable sharing. While the project's working language is English, you are welcome to speak in your native language or use local cultural expressions. These will be carefully translated and honoured in the final version of the video, so that your voice and meaning are fully respected.

Annex 5 - Subproject 5

Title of the Study: Artists: Re-imagining the Face

Annex 5A. Participant Information Sheet

fAICES – Facial Recognition Technologies. Etho-Assemblages and Alternative Futures (Grant agreement ID: 101140664), funded by the European Research Council

Title of the subproject: Artists: Re-imagining the Face

Principal Investigator: Helena Machado (Helena.Cristina.Machado@iscte-iul.pt), CIES (Centre for Research and Studies in Sociology), Iscte–University Institute of Lisbon, Portugal

Purpose of the Research

This study explores how artists engage with facial recognition technologies through their creative practices. It forms part of the *fAICES* project, funded by the European Research Council, which examines how technological expertise is shaped and contested across different domains—including through artistic reflection, critique, and experimentation.

Our aim is to understand how artistic practices respond to the social, political, and ethical implications of facial recognition—whether by questioning, subverting, or reimagining how these technologies function and what they represent.

You have been invited because your artistic work engages with facial recognition or related technologies. We are interested in your creative approaches, critical perspectives, and the ways your work opens up alternative ways of thinking about technology and its role in society.

Voluntary Participation

Your participation is entirely voluntary. You may refuse to answer any question or withdraw from the study at any time without providing a reason and without facing any negative consequences.

What Participation Involves

You will be invited to participate in a semi-structured interview (either in person or online) lasting approximately 60–90 minutes. With your consent, the interview will be audio-recorded for transcription and analysis.

Confidentiality

Your name and artistic work may be included in research outputs only with your explicit consent. Otherwise, your identity will be anonymised. Any recordings or materials will be securely stored and accessed only by the Principal Investigator and core research team. No data will be used for commercial purposes or shared without consent.

Data Handling and Retention

- Your interview will be conducted either face-to-face or online (using a secure video conferencing platform), depending on the context and your preference. In either case, your responses may be audio recorded and transcribed for research purposes.

- Audio recordings will be securely deleted immediately after transcription and verification. Transcripts and other pseudonymised data will be stored on encrypted, offline devices or on secure institutional servers at Iscte–University Institute of Lisbon. Identifiable personal data will not be stored on external commercial cloud services. Data will be stored only on encrypted devices and on institutional servers and licensed cloud services provided by Iscte (for example, Microsoft 365 / Microsoft Teams), which are protected by contractual and technical safeguards.
- The project is based at Associação Iscte Conhecimento e Inovação – Centro de Valorização e Transferência de Tecnologias (Iscte CI), CIES, Iscte–University Institute of Lisbon, in the European Union, and is therefore subject to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Personal data collected during the research, including from interviews conducted outside the EU, may be transferred to and stored in the EU, where it will be protected through strict security measures, including encryption, pseudonymisation, and restricted access. If no equivalent legal safeguards can be put in place, any international transfer of your data will only occur with your explicit consent, after we explain the possible risks to you.
- If the interview is conducted online, we will use secure, institutionally licensed platforms (such as Microsoft Teams), in line with Iscte’s data protection policies.
- All data will be used solely for research purposes. No identifying information will appear in any publications or presentations. Transcripts will be retained for two years after the end of the project and then permanently and securely deleted.

Use of Artistic Works

You will be asked whether you authorise the inclusion of references, images, or descriptions of your work in academic publications, presentations, or project outputs (e.g., exhibitions). All such uses will be subject to your approval.

Legal Basis and Your Rights

This study complies with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and local data protection laws in each country involved. You have the right to:

- Access your personal data.
- Request correction or deletion of your data (unless already anonymised and published).
- Withdraw consent at any time.
- Withdrawing your consent will not affect the lawfulness of any data processing that took place before your withdrawal.
- If you consider it necessary, you also have the right to lodge a complaint with the competent Data Protection Authority. In Portugal, this is the Portuguese Data Protection Authority (Comissão Nacional de Proteção de Dados – CNPD).

The data controller for this research is Iscte – University Institute of Lisbon (Iscte – Instituto Universitário de Lisboa). Iscte – Instituto Universitário de Lisboa is responsible for deciding how and why your personal data are processed in this project.

For any doubts, concerns or need of additional information, and for any questions about how your personal data are handled or to exercise your data protection rights (access,

rectification, erasure, restriction, objection), please contact the Principal Investigator, Helena Machado (Helena.Cristina.Machado@iscte-iul.pt).

Thank you for reading this information. Please keep this document for your records. The next page contains the consent form.

iscte UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE
OF LISBON

iscte SOCIOLOGY
AND PUBLIC POLICY

cies _ iscte
Centre for Research
and Studies in Sociology

Annex 5B. Consent Form

fAIces – Facial Recognition Technologies. Etho-Assemblages and Alternative Futures (Grant agreement ID: 101140664), funded by the European Research Council

Title of the subproject: Artists: Re-imagining the Face

Principal Investigator: Helena Machado (Helena.Cristina.Machado@iscte-iul.pt), CIES (Centre for Research and Studies in Sociology), Iscte– University Institute of Lisbon, Portugal

Please read each statement and tick the box to confirm your agreement:

- I confirm that I have read and understood the Participant Information Sheet.
- I have had the opportunity to ask questions and received satisfactory answers.
- I voluntarily agree to participate in this study.
- I consent to the audio recording of the interview.
- I understand that the interview may be conducted either in person or online. If the interview is conducted online, a secure, institutionally licensed video-conferencing platform (such as Microsoft Teams) will be used, in accordance with Iscte's data protection and security policies. If it takes place outside the European Economic Area (EEA), I consent to the transfer of my data to the EU, under the safeguards described in the Participant Information Sheet.
- I understand that I can withdraw from the study at any time without giving a reason, and without any negative consequences.
- I understand that the data collected will be used solely for academic research purposes, and that my anonymity and confidentiality will be protected.

Future use and open science

- I agree that fully anonymised data from my participation may be shared in open-access research repositories (such as the Iscte community on Zenodo and the Iscte institutional repository) for future scientific use.
- I do not agree that my anonymised data are made publicly available in open-access repositories. My decision will not affect my participation in this study in any way.

Declaration:

I declare that I have read and understood this document, and the information provided to me verbally. I voluntarily agree to participate in this study, in accordance with the terms outlined above. I authorise the use and dissemination of the research results in academic and scientific contexts, with my identity protected and anonymity guaranteed.

Interviewee's name (Printed): _____

Signature: _____

Date: _____

Interviewer's name (Printed): _____

Signature: _____

Date: _____

Annex 5C. Data Collection Instrument (Interview Guide – Artists)

fAIces – Facial Recognition Technologies. Etho-Assemblages and Alternative Futures (Grant agreement ID: 101140664), funded by the European Research Council

Themes and Sample Questions

1. Artistic Process

- Do you remember the first time you worked with or referred facial recognition in your art? In what circumstances did it happen? Could you tell us a little more about your feelings?
- Are there tensions between representation, consent, and authorship in your work on facial recognition or related technologies? Why?

2. Consent and Authorship Controversies

- What questions, thoughts or provocations related to facial recognition or related technologies are central to your work?
- How do you navigate these issues?

3. Technological Engagement

- Have you directly used facial recognition tools in your practice? If so, in what circumstances? In not, why not?
- How do you position yourself in relation to facial recognition technologies (critically, experimentally, playfully)?
- Looking forward, what do you expect from artists' engagement with facial recognition or related technologies?

4. Publics, ethics and Aesthetics

- Is there any ethical concern related to facial recognition that influence your creative choices? If so, in what way?
- Do you consider your work to be a form of resistance or critique?
- How do publics respond to your work?
- How would you describe the relationship between your work and public interest?

5. Public Engagement

- Have you ever collaborated with scientists or tech companies? If not, why not? If so, how do you engage with scientists or tech companies?
- What about activists or affected communities? Have you ever collaborated with them? If not, why not? If so, how do you engage with activists or affected communities?

Technical and Organisational Safeguards

- Consent-Based Attribution: Participants choose whether to be named or anonymised in all outputs.
- Intellectual Property Respect: Artistic materials (texts, visuals) will only be reproduced or quoted with written permission.
- Access Restriction: Data is accessible only to the PI and Susana Noronha.

- **Storage and Retention:** Materials stored in encrypted, local folders. No external servers used. Deleted two years post-project.
- **Use Limitation:** No materials will be shared with external audiences without prior approval by the artist.
- **Publication Ethics:** Any use of art in exhibitions, publications, or digital platforms will be reviewed with the artist before dissemination.

Annex 6 - Observation Protocol – Scientific, Technological, Activist, and Artistic Events

fAIces – Facial Recognition Technologies. Etho-Assemblages and Alternative Futures (Grant agreement ID: 101140664), funded by the European Research Council

1. General Framework and Objectives

- This protocol outlines procedures for observational research across the *fAIces* project's subprojects. It distinguishes between in-person and digital observational contexts, acknowledging the distinct ethical challenges and safeguards required by each, while maintaining a consistent commitment to research integrity, participant protection, and legal compliance. The overarching aim is to document the discursive, material, and social dimensions of facial recognition technologies as they emerge in public, professional, and artistic spaces.

- Observations may be conducted in both EU and non-EU countries. Regardless of location, the *fAIces* project adheres to the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), as ISCTE – University Institute of Lisbon serves as the data controller. Any data collected outside the EU will be securely transferred to the EU under appropriate safeguards.

- All observation will adhere to principles of transparency, non-intrusiveness, data minimisation, and respect for individual autonomy, in compliance with GDPR, institutional ethics standards, and contextual sensitivity.

2. In-Person Observation

In-person observation will take place at public or semi-public events, including scientific conferences, industry fairs, activist gatherings, community forums, and physical exhibitions.

2.1. Ethical Safeguards

- Observation will be passive and non-intrusive; no private conversations will be recorded.
- Audio or video recordings will only be made with explicit, informed consent (oral or written).
- In public events, consent is not required unless individuals are personally identifiable and captured in the media.
- In semi-public or closed events, observation notices will be provided to organisers and/or visibly displayed.
- No covert observation will be conducted.
- Incidental identification (e.g., names on badges or in Q&A) will be excluded or anonymised in fieldnotes.
- No profiling or automated analysis will be performed.
- Observational data will be securely stored and retained only for the necessary duration, and permanently deleted within two years post-project.
- Any personal data incidentally collected during in-person observation in countries outside the EU will be transferred to the EU for analysis and securely stored on

institutional servers at ISCTE. These international transfers are covered under the project's data protection framework and comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), including the use of appropriate safeguards where applicable.

2.2. Subproject Contexts

2.2.1. Scientific Conferences and Industry Events (Subprojects 1 & 2)

These events provide insights into how facial recognition technologies are framed within science, technology, policy, and ethics communities. Observations will focus on plenaries, panels, exhibitions, and informal interactions. Researchers will document language, visual representations, and material culture (e.g., slides, slogans, booths). Fieldnotes will avoid personal identifiers unless individuals act in public-facing roles.

2.2.2. Advocacy and Activist Spaces (Subproject 3)

These spaces are critical to understanding public resistance to facial recognition technologies. Researchers will observe slogans, banners, organisational methods, and audience reactions, avoiding attribution unless individuals are speaking in public forums (e.g., panels, livestreams). Organisers will be informed in advance where possible, and observation notices will be circulated when appropriate.

2.2.3. Community-Based Observations (Subproject 4)

Community events related to racialised surveillance or everyday facial recognition technologies' use will be observed only with the collaboration of trusted intermediaries and with organiser's consent. Notes will focus on environmental cues, affective atmospheres, and collective expressions, not individual data. Cultural and linguistic sensitivity will guide all interactions.

3. Digital Observation

Digital observation includes livestreamed conferences, online artistic and tech industry exhibitions, and public forums where facial recognition technologies are discussed or represented. The digital context raises distinct ethical questions regarding traceability, platform norms, and visibility.

3.1. Ethical Safeguards

- Only publicly accessible content will be observed unless explicit access is granted.
- No user handles, profile photos, or chat logs will be recorded unless individuals are acting in public roles.
- Screenshots will only be taken if permitted by platform policy or with organiser/artist consent.
- No interaction with participants will occur unless required and consented.
- Platform Terms of Service and community guidelines will be respected.
- Data will be anonymised and securely stored, following GDPR standards.

- If collected from sources outside the EU, data will be transferred to and processed in the EU, with appropriate technical and organisational safeguards in place in line with GDPR requirements.

3.2. Subproject Contexts

3.2.1. Artistic Exhibitions (Subproject 5)

Observation in digital art contexts will focus on curatorial framing, interactive installations, audience reactions (e.g., chat comments), and aesthetic representations of facial recognition technologies. Screenshots will only be taken with permission. No identifiable user data will be retained.

3.2.2. Web Crawling and Online Public Discourse (New Section, if applicable)

If the project includes web-based observation or scraping of public discourse around facial recognition technologies (e.g., hashtags, forums, blogs), data collection will:

- Be limited to publicly available content.
- Avoid personal identifiers.
- Exclude private profiles, DMs, or gated communities.
- Comply with relevant platform and institutional ethical guidelines.

4. Sample Fieldnote Guide

- Date, time, and setting (physical/digital).
- Event type and theme.
- Public/private context and visibility of observation notice.
- Participant demographics (if visible, generalised).
- Key discourses or narratives related to facial recognition technologies.
- Visuals, symbols, or materials used.
- Observed emotional tones (e.g., enthusiasm, resistance).
- Researcher reflection or analytic memo.

5. Confidentiality and Transfer Note

Fieldnotes will be pseudonymised where appropriate and securely transferred to Iscte-University Institute of Lisbon for storage and analysis. No personally identifying details will be included unless individuals act in public-facing roles, and all data will be managed in line with GDPR requirements.

Annex 7 - Privacy and Ethics Notice for Public Online Data Collection (Web Crawling Activities)

fAIces – Facial Recognition Technologies. Etho-Assemblages and Alternative Futures (Grant agreement ID: 101140664), funded by the European Research Council

1. Purpose of this Notice

Under Article 14 of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), data subjects must be informed when their personal data is collected indirectly. Because our project involves collecting publicly available online content through automated techniques (e.g., web crawling), and contacting each individual is not feasible, this notice serves as our method of ensuring transparency.

2. Who We Are

The *fAIces* project is an academic research initiative hosted at Associação Iscte Conhecimento e Inovação – Centro de Valorização e Transferência de Tecnologias (CVTT-ISCTE), CIES, Iscte–University Institute of Lisbon, investigating the societal, ethical, and political dimensions of facial recognition technologies.

The data controller for this research is Iscte – University Institute of Lisbon (Iscte – Instituto Universitário de Lisboa). Iscte – Instituto Universitário de Lisboa is responsible for deciding how and why your personal data are processed in this project.

Principal Investigator: Helena Machado (Helena.Cristina.Machado@iscte-iul.pt)

Data Protection Officer (Iscte): dpo@iscte-iul.pt

3. What Data We Collect and Why

We collect publicly available online content relevant to discussions about facial recognition technologies. This may include:

- Blog posts, news articles, public statements, or press releases.
- Social media posts or comments from public profiles.
- Public comments on forums or news sites.
- Names or professional affiliations if disclosed in a public-facing context.

We do not collect:

- Private, password-protected, or paywalled content (unless access is lawfully granted through institutional subscriptions).
- Biometric or image-based data.
- Sensitive personal data unless it is manifestly made public by the individual.

This data is used strictly for academic, non-commercial research purposes to analyse public and expert discourse on facial recognition.

4. Legal Basis for Processing

Our processing of personal data is based on the following GDPR provisions:

- Article 6(1)(e) – Processing is necessary for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest (scientific research).
- Article 6(1)(f) – Processing is based on legitimate interest in conducting academic research.
- Article 9(2)(j) – Processing of special category data for research purposes, with appropriate safeguards in place.

When notifying individuals directly is not possible, this notice fulfils our duty of transparency under Article 14(5)(b) GDPR, based on the principle of disproportionate effort.

Any further processing of data collected through web crawling for scientific research purposes will follow Article 6(4) GDPR, which sets out the compatibility criteria for further processing. The legal basis is the combination of Article 6(1)(e) GDPR (task carried out in the public interest – scientific research) and Article 89 GDPR (appropriate safeguards for research, such as pseudonymisation, data minimisation, and access controls). Under these conditions, the further use of publicly available online data for research is considered compatible with the original purposes for which the data were made public.

5. Data Safeguards and Retention

We are committed to protecting your privacy. All data:

- Is pseudonymised or anonymised before inclusion in any research output.
- Is stored on encrypted devices or secure institutional servers.
- Is accessible only by the *fAICES* research team.
- Will not be used to profile individuals, make automated decisions, or be commercialised.
- Will be retained only as long as necessary and permanently and securely deleted two years after project completion, in line with Iscte-University Institute of Lisbon’s policies.

6. Your Rights

If you believe your personal data has been collected as part of this research, you may request to:

- Access the data.
- Correct inaccurate information.
- Object to its use for research.
- Request deletion (where legally applicable).

To exercise your rights or raise concerns, please contact:

The Principal Investigator: Helena Machado – Helena.Cristina.Machado@iscte-iul.pt

Annex 8 - Data Protection and Cookies Policy (website)

fAIces – Facial Recognition Technologies. Etho-Assemblages and Alternative Futures (Grant agreement ID: 101140664), funded by the European Research Council

Data Protection and Cookies Policy

fAIces is a non-commercial research project. We are committed to protecting your privacy and handling any personal data responsibly and transparently.

1. Personal Data Collection

We do not actively collect or store personal data through this website. The only personal information we may receive is if you choose to contact us via email. This data is used solely to respond to your inquiry. Email communications are stored only for as long as necessary to handle your request and are not shared or used for any other purpose. For more information, please refer to our Privacy and Ethics Notice for Public Online Data Collection on the official *fAIces* project website (link).

2. Legal Basis

As an academic research initiative, we follow the principles of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and other applicable data protection regulations. We process data on the following legal bases under the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR):

- Website technical data (e.g., temporary IP logs for routing and security): Processed under legitimate interest (Article 6(1)(f) GDPR) to ensure the proper functioning and security of the website.
- Emails and voluntary communication: Processed under legitimate interest (Article 6(1)(f) GDPR), as processing is necessary to respond to requests initiated by the data subject.

3. Data Sharing

We do not sell, rent, or share personal data with third parties.

4. Website Hosting and Security

This website is hosted on Iscte–University Institute of Lisbon’s servers, which may collect standard technical data such as IP addresses or browser type for security and performance purposes. This data is not used to identify individual users.

5. Your Rights

If you contact us and we hold any of your data, you may request access or deletion at any time by emailing the Principal Investigator (Helena Machado): Helena.Cristina.Machado@iscte-iul.pt

Cookies Policy

This website uses only essential cookies necessary for it to function properly. We do not use tracking cookies or analytics tools like Google Analytics.

What Are Cookies?

Cookies are small text files stored on your device by your browser. They help websites operate correctly (e.g., remembering language preferences or keeping the layout consistent).

Types of Cookies We Use:

- **Essential Cookies:** Required for basic site functionality (e.g., navigation, responsiveness). These cookies do not collect personal data and cannot be disabled.

If in the future we introduce additional cookies (e.g., analytics, embedded media), we will update this policy and ask for your consent.

Managing Cookies

Most browsers allow you to manage or block cookies. For more details, visit: <https://www.allaboutcookies.org>

Annex 9A - Confidentiality and Responsibility Agreement for External Service Providers

fAIces – Facial Recognition Technologies. Etho-Assemblages and Alternative Futures (Grant agreement ID: 101140664), funded by the European Research Council

Project Title: *fAIces – Facial Recognition Technologies. Etho-Assemblages and Alternative Futures*

Host Institution: Associação Iscte Conhecimento e Inovação – Centro de Valorização e Transferência de Tecnologias (CVTT-ISCTE)

Principal Investigator: Helena Machado (Centre for Research and Studies in Sociology (CIES-Iscte), University Institute of Lisbon)

Research Grant No.: 101140664 – ERC Advanced Grant

1. Purpose

This agreement sets out the confidentiality and data protection obligations of external service providers (companies or self-employed professionals) who, in the context of services rendered to Iscte for the *fAIces* project, have access to personal data (for example, translation or transcription of interviews, or facilitation of focus groups).

2. Role of the Service Provider

The service provider processes personal data on behalf of and under the documented instructions of Iscte, in accordance with Article 28 of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). These obligations are further specified in the separate data processing contract or equivalent legal instrument concluded between Iscte and the provider.

3. Confidential Information

For the purposes of this agreement, “confidential information” includes, but is not limited to:

- personal data of research participants (e.g. names, contact details, audio/video recordings, interview transcripts);
- special categories of personal data and other sensitive research information;
- any pseudonymised or coded data where re-identification is reasonably possible;
- internal project documentation, analysis notes and communications made available for the performance of the services.

4. Obligations of the Service Provider

The service provider agrees to:

- use personal data solely for the purpose of delivering the contracted services to Iscte in the context of the *fAIces* project and for no other purpose;

- ensure that only personnel who have a strict “need to know” have access to the data, and that such personnel are bound by appropriate confidentiality obligations;
- implement appropriate technical and organisational measures to protect personal data against unauthorised or unlawful processing and against accidental loss, destruction or damage;
- not disclose, copy, store or transfer personal data to any third party or to any country outside the agreed locations, except as explicitly authorised in writing by Iscte;
- promptly inform Iscte of any personal data breach or suspected breach relating to the data processed under this agreement;
- securely delete or return all personal data (and any copies) to Iscte upon completion of the services or upon request, in accordance with Iscte’s written instructions.

5. Duration

These confidentiality and data protection obligations apply throughout the period in which the provider processes personal data for the *fAIces* project and continue to apply indefinitely with regard to any personally identifiable or sensitive information obtained in the course of that work.

6. Applicable Framework

The service provider undertakes to comply with:

- the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR);
- the terms of the data processing contract or equivalent legal instrument concluded with Iscte under Article 28 GDPR;
- Iscte’s written instructions on data protection and information security provided in connection with the *fAIces* project.

Service Provider

Name / Company: _____

Representative (if applicable): _____

Function: _____

Signature: _____

Date: _____

On behalf of Iscte / *fAIces* project

Name: _____

Function: _____

Signature: _____

Date: _____

Annex 9B - Request of Technical and Legal Approval

Gabinete Jurídico

DESPACHO

Processo n° 1044/2025/GJ_MC

Data: 10/12/2025

Assunto: Proposta de Termo de Confidencialidade e Responsabilidade – Anexo 9 do Projeto “fAlces – Facial Recognition Technologies. Etho-Assemblages and Alternative Futures” – Revisão Jurídica.

Informação Jurídica

Foi solicitado a este Gabinete Jurídico que procedesse à análise do assunto supra identificado.

Cumpre-nos, assim, informar:

I. Relatório

1. No âmbito do projeto em referência é remetido para revisão deste Gabinete um Termo de Confidencialidade e Responsabilidade para ser subscrito por prestadores de serviços externos, tais como tradutores, transcritores e outros prestadores de serviços externos que possam ter acesso a dados pessoais no âmbito do projeto.
2. O documento prevê assim que as partes que o vão subscrever, para proteger a sua colaboração, trocarão informações, materiais e dados pessoais cuja confidencialidade se comprometem em proteger.
3. O acordo remetido para revisão jurídica define as suas obrigações e deveres.

II. Legislação aplicável

- A. Código Civil, aprovado pelo Decreto-Lei n.º 47344/66, de 25 de novembro, na sua redação atual – Artigo 405º;
- B. Regulamento Geral de Proteção de Dados Pessoais, aprovado pelo Regulamento (EU) n.º 2016/679, de 27 de abril – Artigos 5, 6º e 28º.

III. Informação

1. O termo de confidencialidade e responsabilidade remetido para revisão jurídica reconduz-se a um contrato, no qual as partes celebram um pacto para manterem determinadas informações em sigilo.
2. Sendo contratos estão sujeitos a vários princípios, sendo que, nesta matéria, o mais relevante é o princípio da liberdade contratual.

3. O Termo de Confidencialidade e Responsabilidade sob revisão jurídica obedece às regras e costumes de um documento desta natureza jurídica.
4. Sublinhe-se que a assinatura do presente termo de responsabilidade e confidencialidade pelos prestadores externos do projeto não dispensa a assinatura de um acordo de subcontratação de dados pessoais tal como previsto no artigo 28º do RGPD.
5. O documento sob revisão merece a validação técnico-jurídica deste Gabinete.

À Consideração Superior.

Marta Correia

Assessora Jurídica | Gabinete Jurídico

Lisboa, 10 de dezembro de 2025

GJ/MC

Annex 10 - Institutional Confidentiality and Responsibility Term for Researchers/Students

“Termo de Responsabilidade e de Confidencialidade do Investigador/Estudante – Tratamento de Dados Pessoais”

This annex reproduces both the original Portuguese version and the English translation of the institutional standard form approved by Iscte for students, researchers, and research collaborators without an employment contract who have access to personal data in the context of scientific projects such as fAIces.

Minuta do Termo de Responsabilidade e de Confidencialidade do Investigador/Estudante – Tratamento de Dados Pessoais

(para estudantes; ou investigadores ou colaboradores em trabalhos de investigação sem contrato de trabalho com o Iscte)

Nome completo do investigador/estudante [selecionar o aplicável]:

Número:

Escola: Escola de Sociologia e Políticas Públicas

Departamento ou Unidade de investigação: Centro de Investigação e Estudos de Sociologia, CIES-Iscte, Iscte, Instituto Universitário de Lisboa.

Título do projeto de investigação científica: *fAIces – Facial Recognition Technologies. Etho-Assemblages and Alternative Futures* (Grant agreement ID: 101140664), com financiamento do European Research Council, PI: Helena Machado,

No desenvolvimento do projeto de investigação científica já identificado são obrigações do investigador/estudante [selecionar o aplicável] as seguintes:

1. Garantir a prática de boas condutas no desenvolvimento do projeto de investigação aqui em causa, designadamente, assegurando o cumprimento da legislação e das orientações internas do Iscte relativas ao tratamento de dados pessoais, promovendo a identificação e a prevenção de riscos.
2. Os dados pessoais a que o signatário tem acesso, no âmbito do desenvolvimento do projeto de investigação supra identificado, apenas podem ser tratados para esse fim.
3. Aceder apenas aos dados que sejam adequados, pertinentes e limitados ao que é estritamente necessário para o desenvolvimento do projeto de investigação, tendo

em vista as finalidades legítimas e específicas do tratamento para os quais foram recolhidos, dando assim cumprimento ao princípio da minimização dos dados.

4. Adotar as melhores medidas técnicas e organizativas a fim de assegurar o respeito pelos princípios da proteção de dados pessoais, incluindo, quando possível, a sua anonimização ou pseudonimização, bem como a sua encriptação.
5. O investigador/estudante [selecionar o aplicável] só poderá tratar os dados pessoais necessários para o desenvolvimento do projeto de investigação na medida em que se verifique pelo menos uma das condições de licitude para o tratamento previstas no art. 6º do RGPD, ou uma das exceções previstas no art. 9º do RGPD.
6. Caso o investigador/estudante [selecionar o aplicável] trate dados pessoais em larga escala relacionados com condenações penais, infrações ou com medidas de segurança ao abrigo do artigo 10º do RGPD, ou caso o tratamento seja suscetível de resultar num elevado risco para os direitos e liberdades das pessoas singulares nos termos do artigo 35º do RGPD, o investigador/estudante [selecionar o aplicável] deve elaborar e submeter à coordenação do projeto/ao seu orientador [selecionar o aplicável], uma proposta de avaliação de impacto sobre a proteção de dados, antes de iniciar o tratamento.
7. Adotar as medidas de segurança técnicas e organizativas adequadas de forma a que seja garantida a integridade e confidencialidade dos dados, aqui se incluindo a proteção contra o seu tratamento não autorizado ou ilícito, contra a sua perda, destruição ou danificação accidental, devendo ser evitado o tratamento, nomeadamente o acesso e utilização dos mesmos, por pessoas não autorizadas.
8. Comprometer-se a respeitar as normas de segurança, restrições de sistema e as boas práticas de segurança da informação em vigor nesta instituição de ensino, designadamente:
 - i. A não se ausentar do seu posto de trabalho sem encerrar a sessão de acesso ao sistema informático, garantindo assim a impossibilidade de acesso indevido por terceiros.
 - ii. A não revelar a sua senha de acesso ao sistema informático a ninguém, garantindo, assim, a impossibilidade de acesso indevido por terceiros.
 - iii. A alterar a sua senha de acesso ao sistema informático sempre que tal seja exigido pelo próprio sistema ou em caso de suspeita de conhecimento da mesma por parte de terceiros.
 - iv. A encriptar os dados pessoais nos dispositivos onde estão armazenados e garantir a proteção das chaves adequadamente.
9. A obrigação de confidencialidade e de responsabilidade é extensível a quaisquer membros da equipa técnica do investigador/estudante [selecionar o aplicável],

caso existam, devendo esta obrigação ser atestada por meio de documento escrito assinado por cada um dos membros.

10. Os titulares, cujos dados são objeto de tratamento pelo investigador/estudante [selecionar o aplicável], têm o direito de acesso, retificação, apagamento e oposição, limitação do tratamento e à portabilidade dos seus dados pessoais, nos termos definidos no projeto de investigação científica, e de acordo com o disposto nos artigos 16º a 20º do RGPD e as normas específicas previstas na Lei de Execução 58/2019 do RGPD na ordem jurídica nacional.
11. Quando o investigador/estudante [selecionar o aplicável] entender dever responder negativamente a um pedido de exercício de direitos pelos titulares dos dados, cujo tratamento tem a seu encargo no desenvolvimento do projeto de investigação, deve consultar previamente a coordenação do projeto/o seu orientador [selecionar o aplicável].
12. O investigador/estudante [selecionar o aplicável] tratará os dados pessoais a que tiver acesso por um período definido pelo projeto de investigação e não superior ao necessário para essa finalidade; caso exista norma legal aplicável que defina um prazo de retenção dos dados tratados superior ao prazo definido pelo projeto, os dados deverão ser conservados durante todo o período legalmente previsto.
13. Determinada a irrelevância da sua conservação no âmbito do projeto de investigação supra citado, ou terminado o período legal de retenção caso exista, quaisquer dados pessoais que estejam na posse do investigador/estudante [selecionar o aplicável] são, de acordo com o que for definido no projeto de investigação:
 - a) Apagados de forma segura ou destruídos;
 - b) Anonimizados.
14. Caso o investigador/estudante [selecionar o aplicável] tenha conhecimento de falhas, reais ou potenciais, relativas à segurança dos sistemas informáticos do Iscte e/ou à proteção de dados pessoais deverá comunicá-las de imediato aos serviços competentes, isto é, os SIIC, e notificar o Encarregado de Proteção de Dados do ISCTE.

Este documento – termo de responsabilidade e confidencialidade – poderá ser alterado a qualquer momento por motivos de ordem legal, segurança ou qualquer outro que vise a melhoria dos interesses de todas as partes envolvidas.

Lisboa, [dia] de [mês] de [Ano]

**Institutional Confidentiality and Responsibility Term for Researchers/Students –
Processing of Personal Data**

**(for students; or researchers or collaborators in research projects without an
employment contract with Iscte)**

Full name of the researcher/student [select as applicable]:

Number:

School:

Department or Research Unit:

Title of the scientific research project: *fAIces – Facial Recognition Technologies. Etho-Assemblages and Alternative Futures (Grant agreement ID: 101140664)*, funded by the European Research Council, PI: Helena Machado, CIES-Iscte, Centre for Research and Studies in Sociology, School of Sociology and Public Policy, Iscte – University Institute of Lisbon.

Within the development of the above-identified scientific research project, the obligations of the researcher/student [select as applicable] are the following:

1. To ensure good conduct in the development of the research project in question, namely by ensuring compliance with legislation and internal Iscte guidelines relating to the processing of personal data, promoting the identification and prevention of risks.
2. The personal data to which the signatory has access, within the scope of the above-identified research project, may only be processed for that purpose.
3. To access only the data that are adequate, relevant and limited to what is strictly necessary for the development of the research project, in line with the legitimate and specific purposes for which they were collected, thus complying with the data minimisation principle.
4. To adopt the best technical and organisational measures to ensure respect for the principles of personal data protection, including, where possible, their anonymisation or pseudonymisation, as well as their encryption.
5. The researcher/student [select as applicable] may only process the personal data necessary for the development of the research project insofar as at least one of the lawful bases for processing set out in Article 6 of the GDPR applies, or one of the exceptions set out in Article 9 of the GDPR.

6. If the researcher/student [select as applicable] processes large-scale personal data relating to criminal convictions, offences or security measures under Article 10 of the GDPR, or if the processing is likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons under Article 35 of the GDPR, the researcher/student [select as applicable] must prepare and submit to the project coordination/their supervisor [select as applicable] a data protection impact assessment proposal before beginning the processing.
7. To adopt appropriate technical and organisational security measures to ensure the integrity and confidentiality of the data, including protection against unauthorised or unlawful processing, and against accidental loss, destruction or damage, and to prevent processing—namely access to and use of the data—by unauthorised persons.
8. To commit to respecting the security rules, system restrictions and information security best practices in force at this higher education institution, namely:
 - i. Not leaving their workstation without logging out of the IT system, thus preventing unauthorised access by third parties.
 - ii. Not disclosing their IT system login password to anyone, thus preventing unauthorised access by third parties.
 - iii. Changing their IT system password whenever required by the system itself or in case of suspected disclosure to third parties.
 - iv. Encrypting personal data stored on devices and ensuring the adequate protection of encryption keys.
9. The duty of confidentiality and responsibility extends to any members of the researcher's/student's technical team [select as applicable], if any, and this obligation must be documented by a written document signed by each member.
10. Data subjects whose personal data are processed by the researcher/student [select as applicable] have the right of access, rectification, erasure, objection, restriction of processing and portability of their personal data, under the terms defined in the scientific research project and in accordance with Articles 16 to 20 of the GDPR and the specific provisions set out in the GDPR Implementation Law 58/2019 in the national legal order.
11. Whenever the researcher/student [select as applicable] considers responding negatively to a request by a data subject exercising their rights regarding the data processed within the development of the research project, they must first consult the project coordination/their supervisor [select as applicable].
12. The researcher/student [select as applicable] shall process the personal data to which they have access for a period defined by the research project and no longer than necessary for that purpose; if there is an applicable legal rule that determines a retention period longer than that defined by the project, the data must be kept for the full legally-established period.
13. Once the data are no longer relevant for the purposes of the above-cited research project, or once the legal retention period has expired, if applicable, any personal

data held by the researcher/student [select as applicable] shall, as defined in the research project:

- a) Be securely erased or destroyed; or
- b) Be anonymised.

14. If the researcher/student [select as applicable] becomes aware of actual or potential failures relating to the security of Iscte's IT systems and/or to the protection of personal data, they must immediately report them to the competent services, i.e., SIIC, and notify the Data Protection Officer of Iscte.

This document – Confidentiality and Responsibility Term – may be amended at any time for legal, security, or other reasons intended to improve the interests of all parties involved.

Lisbon, [day] of [Month] of [Year]

Annex 11 - Team Roles and Access to Personal Data

fAIces – Facial Recognition Technologies. Etho-Assemblages and Alternative Futures
(Grant agreement ID: 101140664), funded by the European Research Council

1. Purpose

This document defines and distinguishes between team members and collaborators within the *fAIces* research project. It establishes expectations regarding responsibilities, data access, and authorship eligibility in alignment with ethical and institutional research standards.

2. Role Definitions

2.1. Team Members

A team member is a researcher who:

- Is formally employed, contracted, or funded through the *fAIces* project.
- Is listed in project deliverables or grant documentation.
- Is subject to *fAIces* institutional and ethical oversight.

Team members:

- Have access to all internal documents, raw empirical materials, and tools.
- Are involved in the design, data collection, analysis, and publication processes.
- Are expected to follow *fAIces* research ethics, authorship, and data-sharing policies.
- Are accountable under institutional codes of conduct and research integrity.

2.2. Collaborators

A collaborator is a researcher who:

- Is not employed or funded by *fAIces*.
- Contributes to specific outputs (e.g., joint papers, conceptual consultation, invited analysis).
- Is not involved in the core design, governance, or internal management of *fAIces* activities.

Collaborators:

- May not access raw empirical materials collected by the *fAIces* team unless a specific agreement is in place.
- May contribute to publications and be considered for authorship if they meet established criteria.
- Must be properly acknowledged or listed based on actual contribution.
- Are not entitled to internal documentation or governance decisions.

3. Data Access

Role	Access to Raw Data	Requires Data Agreement
Team Member	Yes	Internal policies apply
Collaborator	Not by default	If access is granted

4. Authorship Eligibility

Authorship is determined by the criteria in the *fAICES* internal document *Guidelines for Authorship and Writing*. These guidelines will also be shared with collaborators. Meeting the criteria — not employment status — determines eligibility for authorship.

5. Oversight

The Principal Investigator (PI) is responsible for determining role assignments. The list of team members and collaborators should be updated as the project evolves. Any questions about status, access, or authorship should be raised early and documented.

Annex 12 - Data Management Plan

*fAices – Facial Recognition Technologies. Etho-Assemblages and Alternative Futures
(Grant agreement ID: 101140664), funded by the European Research Council*

European Research Council
Executive Agency

Established by the European Commission

European Research Council (ERC)

ERC Data Management Plan

Template

ERC OPEN RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN (DMP)

Project Acronym	Project Number
<i>fAIces</i>	Grant ID: 101140664

Template for the ERC Open Research Data Management Plan (DMP). The following sections should describe how you plan to make the project data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR). Each of the following five issues should be addressed with a level of detail appropriate to the project.

SUMMARY (*dataset reference and name; origin and expected size of the data generated/collected; data types and formats*)

The *fAIces* project explores the social, ethical, and political implications of facial recognition technologies through qualitative, multi-sited research. Participants include scientists, technologists, artists, activists, and Black communities across Europe and the Americas. The project will curate a single integrated corpus, FAICES-DATASET-001.

The project will generate original data through:

- Semi-structured interviews
- Focus groups
- Ethnographic observation (in-person and digital)
- Document analysis
- Web crawling (only from public sources)
- Co-produced video and visual materials

Data formats will include:

- Audio recordings (.mp3), transcripts (.txt/.docx)
- Fieldnotes and logs (.txt/.pdf)
- Annotated documents (.pdf/.docx)
- Focus group artifacts
- Visual and audiovisual files (.jpg/.mp4)
- Web-scraped textual data (.csv/.json)

To ensure long-term preservation and accessibility, commonly used proprietary or compressed formats (e.g., .mp3, .mp4, .docx, .pdf) will be converted to open, sustainable formats where appropriate. These include, for example, .wav for audio, .txt or .odt for text, .tiff or .png for images, and PDF/A for documents. All data will adhere to best practices in data stewardship and will follow recommendations for open formats as outlined by DANS (<https://dans.knaw.nl/en/file-formats>).

Estimated size: ~100 interviews, 8–10 focus groups, extensive fieldnotes, and media outputs.

All files will be accompanied by rich machine-readable metadata (Dublin Core + DDI) in .xml or .json; persistent identifiers (DOI) will be minted on Zenodo immediately upon first deposit. CC BY 4.0 (or CC 0 for non-sensitive web-scraped data) will be the default licence. Data will be stored on encrypted institutional servers to guarantee data security.

1. MAKING DATA FINDABLE (*dataset description: metadata, persistent and unique identifiers e.g., DOI*)

- **Repository & PID infrastructure:** All public (or embargoed-metadata-only) datasets will be deposited, anonymized, in the Zenodo “Iscte” community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/iscte/>), which automatically issues DOIs and interoperates with the EOSC federation. Internal versions live on encrypted institutional servers (Iscte IT infrastructure).

Metadata standard: Dublin Core elements mapped to the Data Documentation Initiative (DDI-Codebook) where applicable; ORCID iDs for researchers; controlled vocabularies from EU Vocabularies and CESSDA. For the metadata we will use DataCite Metadata Schema v4. This metadata standard is supported by Zenodo. Some advantages of this metadata schema: data objects will be assigned with a globally unique identifier - DOI; ORCID identifier of creator; ROR for organisation; access right; license; version of the resource; etc. (<https://about.zenodo.org/principles/>).

- **Catalogue & versioning:** A live, citable catalogue (CSV + HTML) will be stored alongside the data. Every dataset’s read-me file will summarise methodology, file structure, licence, embargo status, checksum and version history.
- **Documentation:** The datasets will be accompanied by a README file with a description of the data.

2. MAKING DATA OPENLY ACCESSIBLE *(which data will be made openly available and if some datasets remain closed, the reasons for not giving access; where the data and associated metadata, documentation and code are deposited (repository?); how the data can be accessed (are relevant software tools/methods provided?)*

The project follows the principle of “as open as possible, as closed as necessary.”

- **Open access content** will include anonymised interview transcripts, cleaned fieldnotes, non-sensitive observation summaries, methodological appendices, blank consent templates, and all web-scraped textual data that are already in the public domain. These records will be released under a Creative Commons Attribution licence that permits broad reuse with proper citation.
- **Controlled access content** data includes raw audio and video recordings that may contain biometric identifiers, as well as any materials whose disclosure could pose a risk to marginalised participants. In line with Zenodo’s data policies, such non-anonymised or sensitive data will not be uploaded to the repository itself. Instead, a metadata-only record will be created in Zenodo, including a “request access” option.
- Researchers wishing to access these data will be required to sign a bespoke data-use agreement, which will be reviewed and approved by the Principal Investigator and Iscte’s Data Protection Officer. The actual data files will be stored securely in institutional infrastructure and only shared directly with approved requesters.
- **Collaboratively authored artistic outputs** (for example, short documentaries) will be shared under Creative Commons licences that respect the wishes of co-creators - typically CC BY for general dissemination or CC BY-NC when commercial reuse is not desired.

Documentation sufficient for independent re-analysis - interview guides, codebooks, de-identification protocols - will be bundled with each release. Where software applications or proprietary packages were used for analysis, the accompanying read-me will indicate the version and provide pointers to open-source alternatives where possible. It will be included a blank copy of the consent form used as part of the documentation. To ensure that anonymised data can be made available for future reuse, it will be included in the consent a consent sentence for this purpose.

Although the project aims to make anonymised data available via Open Access, individual-level records from potentially vulnerable populations (e.g., focus group transcripts from Subproject 4 – Black Communities) will undergo further aggregation, paraphrasing, or redaction to eliminate re-identification risks. Even anonymised datasets that retain rich contextual detail will be subject to controlled access, evaluated on a case-by-case basis, and shared only under data use agreements with prior ethical review.

All web-scraped data will originate from publicly accessible sources (e.g., news articles, public blog posts, press statements) and will be filtered to exclude personal opinions, indirect identifiers, and user-generated content (e.g., comment sections). In accordance with GDPR Article 14, a Privacy and Ethics Notice is published on the project website, describing the categories of data, legal basis, safeguards, and rights of data subjects. Public availability does not exempt the project from ethical responsibility, and pseudonymisation and documentation protocols are applied before dissemination.

3. MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE *(which standard or field-specific data and metadata vocabularies and methods will be used)*

Interoperability is achieved by:

- Storing textual and numeric materials in non-proprietary, preservation-friendly formats such as .csv, .json, .txt, and PDF/A, and audiovisual materials in widely supported, open or semi-standard formats such as FLAC, or Matroska (.mkv) — in line with DANS recommendations for preferred formats for long-term accessibility and preservation.
- Expressing metadata in Dublin Core XML, with DDI elements added for social-science specificity.
- Employing EU controlled vocabularies for place names, thematic descriptors, and languages (ISO 639-3).
- Maintaining an English-language codebook that explains every variable, analytic code, and relationship across the corpus, allowing seamless ingestion into common CAQDAS packages and facilitating integration with CESSDA-aligned repositories.

Zenodo makes data interoperable by offering export to Dublin Core metadata schema. Metadata in the Iscte Zenodo community will be harvested by the Iscte CRIS system and migrated to the Iscte institutional repository for long-term preservation.

4. INCREASE DATA RE-USE (*what data will remain re-usable and for how long, is embargo foreseen; how the data is licensed; data quality assurance procedures*)

Anonymised and pseudonymised datasets will be released as soon as practicable and no later than one year after collection, unless specific ethical or legal factors require a brief embargo. All open files will carry a CC BY 4.0 licence; web-scraped text that is already public will be waived into the public domain via CC 0. In circumstances where participants request non-commercial restrictions on co-created media, the project will apply CC BY-NC 4.0 and explain the rationale in the metadata.

Robust quality-assurance procedures underpin reusability. Transcripts undergo double verification; automated and manual sweeps remove direct identifiers; audio and video are inspected to confirm that face- or voice-distortion has been applied where promised.

Once released, datasets will remain available for at least ten years in accordance with institutional policy. Continued preservation beyond that horizon will be determined in consultation with the repository and relevant disciplinary bodies.

It will be included a blank copy of the consent form used as part of the documentation.

To ensure that anonymised data can be made available for future reuse, it will be included in the consent a consent sentence for this purpose. For surveys where no personal data is collected the survey introduction should state that taking part in the survey implies consent for the data being used for certain purposes. Any plans for future data sharing will be mentioned.

The project's consent forms include explicit provisions for future data reuse and Open Access publication of anonymised content. For co-produced outputs, such as community video interviews, participants retain the right to review and approve final materials prior to dissemination. Where individuals decline public release, these records will be excluded from Open Access and retained only for internal analysis.

5. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES and DATA SECURITY *(estimated costs for making the project data open access and potential value of long-term data preservation; procedures for data backup and recovery; transfer of sensitive data and secure storage in repositories for long term preservation and curation)*

Responsibility for day-to-day data management rests with the principal investigator and the core research team. They will carry out anonymisation, secure storage, routine back-ups, and the preparation of metadata and documentation. The team is supported by three institutional pillars: the Data Protection Officer, who advises on GDPR compliance and approves any data-transfer agreements; the Ethics Committee, which reviews and monitors participant-protection measures throughout the project; and the IT Services (SIIC), which provide the encrypted server environment, automated back-up regime, and technical troubleshooting.

Every file - raw or processed - resides on encrypted institutional servers to which only authorised team members have access, each bound by a written confidentiality undertaking. Pseudonymisation is carried out at the earliest practical stage, so that direct identifiers are stripped before data circulate internally. Cloud storage is deliberately avoided; when files must travel between partners, they are moved exclusively through end-to-end-encrypted channels, with additional safeguards such as one-time passwords for decryption keys. The deletion policy reflects both ethical commitments and regulatory requirements: personal data that could re-identify participants are securely erased no later than two years after the formal project close-out, or sooner if a participant requests withdrawal. An auditable log records every deletion event.

Where data need to cross borders outside the European Economic Area, the project secures explicit informed consent from the individuals concerned, employs Standard Contractual Clauses to satisfy GDPR Article 46, and, when relevant, obtains local ethics clearance and engages community representatives to ensure culturally appropriate handling. This resource plan, together with the layered security architecture, guarantees that data are managed responsibly, kept safe during their active life, and either preserved in a properly de-identified form or irreversibly destroyed in accordance with participants' rights and the project's scientific obligations.

For datasets that include testimonies or experiential data from vulnerable participants, even after anonymisation, a controlled access model will be preferred over fully open sharing. This model ensures data remains protected while enabling scientific reuse under ethical conditions and in line with participant expectations.

DISCLAIMER:

This Data Management Plan does not substitute for ethics compliance. It remains the responsibility of the Principal Investigator to engage the ERC Ethics Team regarding any concerns over data collection, processing, sharing, and storage in this project.

Annex 13 - Unexpected Findings Procedure and Disclosure Policy (fAICES)

13.1 Purpose and scope

This Annex operationalises the project’s Unexpected Findings Procedure and Disclosure Policy, as required by the ERC ethics screening. It applies to all phases of the project (recruitment, interviews, focus groups, observation, web-based data collection, data processing/analysis, storage, sharing within the team, and dissemination/publication). The purpose is to ensure a timely, documented, harm-minimising response to any unanticipated event or information that may increase ethical, legal, safety, or reputational risks.

13.2 Definition of “unexpected findings” in fAICES

For the purposes of this project, an unexpected finding is any information, event, request, or incident arising during the research that was not anticipated in the Ethics Protocol and that may:

- increase risks to participants, communities, researchers, or third parties;
- affect GDPR compliance or other legal/ethical obligations;
- require changes to recruitment, consent, data handling, or dissemination practices.

Unexpected findings include (non-exhaustive):

1. Imminent or credible risk of harm

- Disclosure of threats of violence, coercion, stalking, or reprisals;
- Indications of acute safeguarding concerns involving a participant or third parties.

2. Heightened safety/reprisals risk linked to identifiability

- Contextual details (even if names are removed) that could enable identification of activists/community members;
- Requests for attribution or public visibility that appear to increase risk.

3. Unanticipated collection or disclosure of unnecessary personal/special-category data

- Accidental recording of identifying details beyond what is necessary;
- Unexpected emergence of special-category data (e.g., political opinions, health status, religious beliefs) beyond the study’s needs;
- In Subproject 4, additional sensitivity where discussions may relate to racial/ethnic identity and discrimination.

4. Third-party requests for data

- Requests from organisations, employers, authorities, media, or other participants for access to recordings, transcripts, or identifiable information.

5. **Unforeseen local legal/ethical constraints**

- New information indicating that additional local approvals are required;
- Restrictions on recording/participation that alter the risk profile of a site.

6. **Data incident / security breach**

- Loss/theft of devices, compromised accounts, misdirected sharing links, unauthorised access to restricted folders, or similar.

7. **Emergent misuse/misrepresentation risk**

- A draft output, quote, vignette, or dataset that could stigmatise groups, enable targeting/surveillance, or be easily weaponised if released as planned.

13.3 Core principles

All responses follow these principles:

- **Safety and dignity first** (participants and communities);
- **Data minimisation** and least intrusive handling;
- **Confidentiality by default** and “need-to-know” access;
- **Proportionality** (actions and disclosures limited to what is necessary);
- **Accountability** through documented decisions and secure record-keeping;
- **Consultation** with appropriate institutional bodies (Data Protection Officer and/or Ethics Committee) and, where relevant, local ethical support partners.

13.4 Triage levels

Unexpected findings are triaged by the PI (in consultation where relevant) into one of the following levels:

- **Level 1 – Low:** minor deviation, no material increase in risk (e.g., an unnecessary identifier appears in transcript → redact).
- **Level 2 – Moderate:** potential risk/compliance implications requiring mitigation and/or consultation (e.g., unanticipated special-category data, uncertainties about local approvals, heightened identifiability risks).
- **Level 3 – High:** imminent risk of serious harm, credible reprisals risk, significant data incident, or high misuse risk requiring immediate containment and escalation.

13.5 Stepwise procedure (workflow)

Step 1 – Pause and contain (immediate).

Stop the relevant activity to prevent escalation (e.g., pause recording; stop processing/sharing a file; postpone planned dissemination; restrict access to materials).

Step 2 – Record a minimal internal note (same day).

Create a short factual note capturing: date, subproject/activity, type of issue, and immediate action taken. Avoid adding unnecessary identifiable details.

Step 3 – Notify the PI (as soon as possible).

The researcher informs the PI promptly. For Level 3 cases, notification is immediate.

Step 4 – Rapid risk assessment and triage (PI).

The PI assesses potential risks (participant safety, identifiability, GDPR/legal obligations, reputational and misuse risks) and assigns Level 1/2/3.

Step 5 – Consultation (as applicable).

Depending on the case, the PI consults one or more of the following:

- **Host Institution Data Protection Officer (DPO)** (especially for data incidents, special-category data issues, transfers, access controls);
- **Host Institution Ethics Committee / competent ethics body** (especially for participant safety, protocol changes, site constraints);
- **Local ethical support partner** (Subproject 4 or other site-based support where relevant);
- **Scientific Advisory Board** input may be requested only in anonymised/aggregated form, when useful for mitigation planning, to avoid unnecessary exposure.

Step 6 – Decision and mitigation measures.

One or more of the following actions may be adopted:

- Redact identifiers; exclude segments; strengthen pseudonymisation;
- Separate key files; tighten access permissions; revise storage/sharing settings;
- Modify interview guide/observation plan; revise consent language or process;
- Switch from video to audio-only (or no recording) where needed;
- Pause or redesign dissemination outputs; introduce additional internal review;
- Seek additional local approvals/authorisations or adjust site selection;
- Implement data incident response measures consistent with institutional procedures.

Step 7 – Participant communication (when appropriate).

Participants are informed when the issue affects their rights, safety, consent choices, or data handling, unless doing so would create additional risk. Communication should be clear, non-alarming, and limited to what is necessary.

Step 8 – Documentation and logging (mandatory).

The PI ensures that the case, decisions, and rationale are recorded in the Unexpected Findings Log (Section 13.7) and that any updated safeguards are incorporated into project practice.

Step 9 – ERC/ERCEA notification (when required).

If an unexpected finding results in material changes to the ethics risk profile or requires amendments to the Ethics Protocol, the PI will notify ERCEA/ERC Ethics in line with ERC requirements and will implement any requested updates.

13.6 Disclosure policy

The project adopts a minimal, harm-reducing disclosure approach.

A. Default rule: confidentiality and need-to-know

Information about unexpected findings is restricted to the PI and those strictly necessary to manage the issue (e.g., DPO/Ethics Committee/local partner). Team discussions should avoid identifiable details unless essential.

B. Disclosure to participants

Participants may be informed when:

- the issue concerns their data protection rights (e.g., correction, withdrawal options, changes in processing);
- the issue concerns their safety or wellbeing;
- additional consent or clarification is needed. Participants will not be burdened with unnecessary detail, and communications will avoid creating fear or pressure. If informing the participant could reasonably increase risk (e.g., reprisals), consultation will guide the safest approach.

C. Disclosure to institutional bodies

The DPO and/or Ethics Committee are informed when:

- there is a data incident or suspected breach;
- special-category data issues exceed what is anticipated/necessary;
- local legal/ethical constraints require changes;
- a case is Level 2/3 or indicates a need to amend procedures or forms.

D. Disclosure to third parties

The project does not disclose identifiable data (recordings, transcripts, raw notes, identifiers, key files) to third parties (including organisations, employers, media, or other participants), except where:

- disclosure is required by law, and

- this is done following consultation with the Host Institution’s competent bodies (DPO/Ethics/legal support as applicable),
- and only the minimum necessary information is disclosed.

E. Serious risk scenarios

Where there is a credible and imminent risk of serious harm, the project will follow a harm-minimisation approach: encourage/support the participant to access appropriate support; consult the competent institutional bodies/local partner; and take further steps only where strictly necessary and proportionate.

13.7 Unexpected Findings Log (template)

The PI maintains a secure log (access-restricted) documenting unexpected findings and responses.

Field	Entry
Case ID	
Date	
Subproject/activity	
Level (1–3)	
What happened (minimal)	
Immediate action	
Consulted (PI/DPO/Ethics/local)	
Decision/mitigation	
Participant informed? (Y/N + how)	
External disclosure? (Y/N + to whom + basis)	
Closure date	

13.8 Training, review and continuous improvement

All team members will be briefed on this Annex before starting fieldwork and again prior to each major data collection phase. The PI will review the log periodically to identify recurring issues and update safeguards, instruments, or guidance where necessary. Any substantive change affecting ethics risks will be reflected in the Ethics Protocol and, where required, communicated to ERCEA.

Annex 14 - ERC Ethics Summary Report

European Research Council
Executive Agency
Established by the European Commission

EUROPEAN RESEARCH COUNCIL EXECUTIVE AGENCY (ERCEA)

Unit B1 – Ethics Review and Expert Management

Dear principal investigator,

Dear representative of the host institution,

We have now finalised the ethics review process of your proposal. Please find attached the ethics summary report. It provides an analysis of the ethics issues involved in your proposal, and it may bring some particular concerns to your attention.

No further action is required from you before the signature of the Grant Agreement.

The responsibility for an ethically sound implementation of the project lies with the scientists and organisations that carry out the work. However, contractually, the responsibility lies with the Host Institution as signatory of the Grant Agreement. Collectively, the beneficiaries carry the responsibility to follow the ethical provisions laid out in, and deriving from, the Horizon Europe Framework Programme.

ERC grants have a long duration and offer considerable freedom to the Investigator(s) to (re) direct the research. Should the research develop in directions that raise additional ethics questions - not covered in this report – this should be brought to the attention of the ERCEA, either by means of an amendment, or informally by contacting the ERCEA Ethics Sector (ERC-ETHICS-MONITORING@ec.europa.eu, 101140664_fAlces in subject line).

With kind regards,

Raluca IONESCU
Head of Unit

Ethics Summary Report

Grant 101140664 - fAlces

Proposal Title	Facial Recognition Technologies. Etho-Assemblages and Alternative Futures
Applicant Name	Helena MACHADO
Panel	SH3
Call	ERC-2023-ADG

Abstract

Facial recognition technologies collect billions of faces that are stored for multiple uses spanning individual identification and tracking, to training of deep neural networks, the mainstay of modern artificial intelligence (AI). From tagging a photo on social media or unlocking a computer, to controversial applications of facial recognition in public spaces, schools, workplaces, and law enforcement activities, facial processing technologies have entered almost every aspect of our lives. While expected benefits relate to security and safety, critics highlight that these technologies normalize surveillance and erode privacy, exacerbate discrimination, and contain insurmountable flaws and inaccuracy. The fAlces project asks: What matters in facial recognition technologies, and why? How politics of mattering enact diverse ways of being implicated? Which forms of citizenship and public engagement are affected? How multiple and complex ethical choices emerge? This study develops a novel methodology by which the perspectives of social groups that have never been studied together, which are jointly but antagonistically implicated in facial recognition technologies, are taken into consideration: scientists who conduct research on facial recognition; professionals working in start-ups and technology companies; members of advocacy groups and activists; black communities; and artists who incorporate facial recognition in their work. The fAlces project will produce an innovative social theory of the face through the combination of a new conceptual approach – “etho-assemblages”, which transgresses the idea of pre-given fixed and dichotomic ethical principles – and the generation of original empirical data. Major outcomes are based on expanding ethics and imagining alternative futures, fueling citizenship and public engagement, and fostering opportunities for academic thinking to be inspired by activism, underrepresented groups, and artistic practices.

Ethics Issues

On the basis of the proposal's methodology and the ethics self-assessment provided, the ethics review identified the following ethics issues:

Humans

- This activity involves human participants
- They are volunteers for social or human sciences research
- They are vulnerable individuals or groups

Protection of personal data

- This activity involves personal data processing
- It involves the processing of special categories of personal data
- It is planned to import personal data from non-EU countries into the EU or from a non-EU country to another non-EU country: The project will not involve the collection and/or processing of personal sensitive data, such as health, sexual lifestyle, religious or philosophical beliefs. Personal data will be gathered to the minimum. Interviewees and participants in the focus groups will be requested to provide their name (which will later be anonymized), gender, information on their educational and professional path, and the actual professional position. These non-sensitive personal data within the focus groups will be collected in Brazil, Canada, France, Germany, the US, Spain, and the UK. Non-sensitive personal data within interviews will be collected in several countries not predicted in advance (where scientists, professionals of start-ups, advocacy and activists, and artists are based).

Non EU countries

- Non-EU countries are involved, some of the activities will be carried out in non-EU countries: Focus groups in the UK, the US, Canada, and Brazil.
- Non-EU countries are involved, the activities undertaken in these countries raise potential ethics issues: Focus groups in the UK, the US, Canada, and Brazil.
- This activity involves low and/or lower-middle income countries, and there are benefit-sharing actions planned

Other ethics issues that should be taken into consideration

Potential misuse of the research and its findings

Ethics analysis

This section summarises and concludes the analysis performed during the ethics review.

The research described in this proposal appears to involve the ethics issues noted in the table above.

The proposal is ethically cleared for granting, in the understanding that the ethics issue will be managed by the Principal Investigator and the institution(s) involved in compliance with the provisions of the Grant Agreement.

We draw your attention to the necessity to ensure, with the assistance of the host institution's Data Protection Officer (whenever applicable), the compliance of the research activities with the General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 (EU GDPR). It is reminded that personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin is a special category of personal data according to Article 9 EU GDPR.

Considering the topic of the research, the research team should be mindful of the potential for misrepresentation and misuse of the research and its findings, especially in the dissemination phase.

An detailed unexpected findings procedure and a related disclosure policy will need to be elaborated and implemented.

Finally, local ethics/research approvals in the countries involved in the research project will need to be obtained prior to fieldwork.

Consequently, the proposal is ethically cleared for granting, in the understanding that the ethics issues will be managed by the PI and the institution(s) involved in compliance with the provisions of the Grant Agreement. All relevant documentation should be kept on file and provided upon request."

This electronic receipt is a digitally signed version of the document submitted by your organisation. Both the content of the document and a set of metadata have been digitally sealed.

This digital signature mechanism, using a public-private key pair mechanism, uniquely binds this eReceipt to the modules of the Funding & Tenders Portal of the European Commission, to the transaction for which it was generated and ensures its full integrity. Therefore a complete digitally signed trail of the transaction is available both for your organisation and for the issuer of the eReceipt.

Any attempt to modify the content will lead to a break of the integrity of the electronic signature, which can be verified at any time by clicking on the eReceipt validation symbol.

More info about eReceipts can be found in the FAQ page of the Funding & Tenders Portal.

<https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/support/faq>

Annex 15 - Data Protection Officer's Opinion

Parecer do Encarregado de Proteção de Dados

Projeto fAlces – Facial Recognition Technologies. Etho-Assemblages and Alternative Futures

Enquadramento

A presente análise baseia-se na documentação fornecida pela equipa de investigação, designadamente o Ethics Protocol for the fAlces Project, versão de setembro de 2025, submetido à apreciação do Encarregado de Proteção de Dados.

1. Resumo do projeto

O projeto fAlces – Facial Recognition Technologies. Etho-Assemblages and Alternative Futures (ERC Advanced Grant n.º 101140664) visa analisar criticamente as tecnologias de reconhecimento facial enquanto fenómeno técnico, social e ético, articulando investigação empírica e conceptual sobre os modos como estas tecnologias moldam práticas científicas, empresariais, artísticas, ativistas e comunitárias.

Trata-se de um projeto de investigação qualitativa, multi-sítio e modular, que recorre a entrevistas semiestruturadas, grupos focais, observação etnográfica presencial e digital, análise documental e web crawling.

O trabalho de campo organiza-se em cinco subprojetos complementares — dedicados, respetivamente, a cientistas, start-ups/empresas, grupos ativistas, comunidades negras (na Europa e América) e artistas — procurando obter uma leitura cruzada das diversas formas de interpretação, envolvimento e/ou resistência em torno do reconhecimento facial.

O projeto prevê a recolha e tratamento de dados pessoais de participantes em diferentes subprojetos, de natureza variável consoante o contexto de investigação, incluindo dados de identificação (nome, género, formação e ocupação profissional), bem como opiniões e experiências sobre o uso, impacto e enquadramento ético-social das tecnologias de reconhecimento facial, e, eventualmente, registos de imagem ou áudio, conforme aplicável a cada caso. O tratamento de dados será realizado exclusivamente para fins de investigação científica.

Considera-se que os dados pessoais recolhidos serão tratados em conformidade com o RGPD e com as medidas de segurança, confidencialidade e conservação descritas no protocolo submetido, incluindo eventuais transferências internacionais asseguradas por salvaguardas legais aplicáveis. De um modo geral, as medidas previstas são adequadas e alinham-se com as orientações em vigor no Iscte, sem prejuízo dos ajustamentos ou medidas adicionais propostos na presente análise.

2. Avaliação de Escala e Identificação de Fatores de Risco nos termos das Orientações do WP29

A dimensão do tratamento previsto no projeto não configura, no seu conjunto, um tratamento em grande escala, atendendo ao número limitado de participantes em cada subprojeto: 60–80 entrevistas individuais com cientistas (Subprojeto 1), 20–30 entrevistas com representantes de startups (Subprojeto 2), 20–30 entrevistas com organizações não-governamentais (Subprojeto 3), três focus groups por país em sete países (Alemanha, Espanha, França, Reino Unido, Brasil, Canadá e EUA), cada um com 6–8 participantes distribuídos por grupos etários (Subprojeto 4), e 20–30 entrevistas individuais com artistas (Subprojeto 5).

Face às orientações do Grupo de Trabalho do Art.º 29, identificam-se, ainda assim, alguns fatores de risco pertinentes: a eventual recolha e tratamento de categorias especiais de dados, dependendo do conteúdo das entrevistas e focus groups; o envolvimento de populações potencialmente vulneráveis no Subprojeto 4; e a recolha e análise de dados publicamente disponíveis, podendo ocorrer cruzamento de bases de dados, ainda que dentro do âmbito do mesmo responsável pelo tratamento, neste caso o Iscte.

Acresce a existência de transferências internacionais de dados, as quais exigem a aplicação das salvaguardas legais adequadas (conforme detalhado nas medidas de controlo e mitigação).

Não se verificam, porém, outros fatores de risco relevantes referidos nas orientações do WP29, como perfilagem, decisões automatizadas com efeitos significativos sobre os participantes, monitorização sistemática de zonas acessíveis ao público ou tratamentos em larga escala.

3. Identificação e síntese dos subprojetos

Os subprojetos apresentam níveis diferenciados de risco potencial (antes da aplicação das medidas previstas pelos investigadores e/ou sugeridas pelo DPO), determinados pela natureza dos dados tratados e pelo contexto das interações com os participantes.

A análise das medidas de controlo e mitigação que reduzem o risco residual para níveis aceitáveis é apresentada nas secções 4 e 5.

Subprojeto 1 – Producing Knowledge, Negotiating Power

Envolve entrevistas semiestruturadas a cientistas e investigadores que trabalham em domínios ligados ao reconhecimento facial, visando compreender práticas de produção de conhecimento, relações institucionais e perceções éticas associadas à investigação neste campo.

Dados recolhidos: identificação profissional, género, percurso académico e opiniões sobre práticas científicas e éticas no domínio do reconhecimento facial, registos de voz.

Nível de risco potencial: baixo.

Subprojeto 2 – Start-Ups and Tech Companies: Turning Code into Products

Inclui entrevistas a profissionais de start-ups e empresas tecnológicas, centradas nos processos de desenvolvimento, comercialização e legitimação de tecnologias de reconhecimento facial e na integração de preocupações éticas e regulatórias.

Dados recolhidos: identificação profissional e opiniões sobre práticas empresariais e decisões ético-técnicas, registos de voz.

Nível de risco potencial: baixo a médio (potenciais implicações reputacionais).

Subprojeto 3 – Advocacy and Activism: Voices of Resistance

Compreende entrevistas a representantes de grupos ativistas e organizações da sociedade civil envolvidos em campanhas ou movimentos de contestação às tecnologias de vigilância e reconhecimento facial.

Dados recolhidos: identificação (opcional, com possibilidade de pseudonimização ou identificação nominal no caso de participantes publicamente ativos), narrativas de resistência, estratégias de ação e perceções éticas e políticas, registos de voz

Nível de risco potencial: médio (possibilidade de exposição pública de posições sensíveis, atendendo ao carácter político e ativista das entrevistas).

Subprojeto 4 – Black Communities: Experiences of Surveillance and Resistance

Assenta em grupos focais e entrevistas com membros de comunidades negras na Europa (França, Alemanha, Espanha e Reino Unido) e nas Américas (Brasil, Canadá e Estados Unidos), com o objetivo de compreender experiências de vigilância, discriminação e resistência associadas ao reconhecimento facial.

A investigação é conduzida com o apoio de organizações locais e cofacilitadores comunitários, incluindo mecanismos de devolução dos resultados em formatos acessíveis e culturalmente adequados.

Dados recolhidos: identificação, opiniões e testemunhos sobre experiências de vigilância, perceções éticas e sociais, registos de voz e imagem (em entrevistas ou vídeos co-produzidos).

Nível de risco potencial: médio-elevado (potencial recolha de dados reveladores de origem étnica e tratamento de informação em contextos geográficos e sociopolíticos sensíveis; Brasil e Estados Unidos não têm decisão de adequação da Comissão Europeia, aplicando-se apenas, no caso dos EUA, um regime restrito a entidades certificadas no

EU–US Data Privacy Framework; a adequação do Canadá é parcial, limitada a organizações abrangidas pela lei federal).

Subprojeto 5 – Artists: Re-imagining the Face

Envolve entrevistas com artistas que integram ou abordam o reconhecimento facial nas suas práticas, podendo incluir a recolha de elementos associados às suas obras, com consentimento, na medida em que estas se encontrem identificadas ou identificáveis como criações do autor participante.

Dados recolhidos: identificação profissional, opiniões sobre o uso e impacto das tecnologias de reconhecimento facial, registos de voz e referências ou imagens das obras artísticas identificadas com o respetivo autor.

Nível de risco potencial: baixo (dados de natureza profissional e recolha de registos limitada a participantes adultos e voluntários, mediante consentimento específico).

Atividade transversal 1 – Web crawling e recolha de dados públicos online

O projeto prevê a recolha e análise de conteúdos publicamente acessíveis na Internet, através de técnicas de web crawling e de mineração de texto e dados (text and data mining), exclusivamente para fins de investigação científica.

A recolha incide sobre informação disponibilizada de forma aberta — como artigos, comunicados, publicações em páginas institucionais ou conteúdos de perfis publicamente acessíveis — e exclui qualquer elemento proveniente de espaços privados ou plataformas que utilizem mecanismos técnicos de exclusão automática (por exemplo, ficheiros robots.txt).

Não se prevê a recolha intencional de categorias especiais de dados, podendo, contudo, ser tratados dados que tenham sido manifestamente tornados públicos pelos próprios titulares, em conformidade com o artigo 9.º, n.º 2, alínea e) do RGPD.

Nível de risco potencial: baixo (dados de natureza pública e tratamento limitado à finalidade de investigação científica; ausência de perfilagem e decisões individuais automatizadas).

Atividade transversal 2 – Observação presencial e digital

Inclui atividades de observação etnográfica em contextos presenciais e digitais, designadamente em conferências, feiras tecnológicas, eventos artísticos ou ativistas, e em espaços online de acesso público relacionados com o tema do reconhecimento facial.

A observação tem natureza não intrusiva e incide sobre dinâmicas coletivas, discursos e práticas em espaços públicos ou semipúblicos, podendo, de forma incidental, abranger

elementos identificativos visíveis nesses contextos (por exemplo, nomes ou imagens expostos publicamente), sem que haja registo sistemático ou focalizado sobre indivíduos.

As notas de campo consistem em descrições contextuais e não incluem identificação direta dos intervenientes, salvo quando estes atuem em funções representativas ou profissionais publicamente reconhecíveis.

Nível de risco potencial: baixo (dados observacionais não identificativos e recolha limitada a contextos públicos ou de acesso aberto).

4. Medidas comuns de controlo e mitigação

As medidas abaixo descritas correspondem, entre outras previstas no protocolo, aos mecanismos de controlo e mitigação de risco definidos pelos investigadores no âmbito do projeto fAlces, com aplicação transversal aos Subprojetos 1 a 5.

No caso específico do Subprojeto 4, encontra-se ainda previsto o acompanhamento e a consulta de entidades e organizações locais nas comunidades participantes, com vista a reforçar a contextualização ética e cultural e a adequação das práticas de recolha de dados.

4.1. Licitude e finalidade do tratamento

- Tratamento realizado exclusivamente para fins de investigação científica, em conformidade com o art.º 89.º do RGPD e com as políticas institucionais do Iscte.
- Base jurídica: consentimento informado dos participantes, nos termos das folhas de informação e formulários de consentimento incluídos nos anexos do protocolo.
- Não há decisões automatizadas, criação de perfis ou utilização comercial dos dados.

4.2. Informação e transparência

- Cada participante recebe ficha de informação ao participante e formulário de consentimento, onde se indicam as finalidades, os contactos da investigadora principal e do Encarregado de Proteção de Dados, os direitos dos titulares, o prazo de conservação, comunicação relativas a transferências internacionais e medidas técnicas e organizativas principais.
- Participação voluntária, com possibilidade de recusar perguntas ou retirar o consentimento a qualquer momento, sem consequências.
- Nos casos em que a utilização de dados identificativos seja relevante para fins de publicações ou divulgação científica (por exemplo, citações atribuíveis, imagens, referências a obras artísticas ou intervenções públicas), o protocolo prevê que tal inclusão seja previamente discutida e acordada com o participante. Em alguns projetos, os participantes podem optar entre anonimato ou identificação, consoante a natureza da sua participação e preferência pessoal, sendo essa escolha respeitada e registada no processo de consentimento.

4.3. Minimização e limitação

- Recolha limitada aos dados estritamente necessários à finalidade de cada subprojeto.
- Separação entre dados identificativos e dados de conteúdo analítico.

4.4. Pseudonimização e separação lógica

- Pseudonimização efetuada após a recolha, conforme previsto no protocolo.
- A chave de correspondência entre identificadores e participantes é guardada separadamente e em local seguro, acessível apenas à investigadora principal e à equipa nuclear.
- As transcrições de entrevistas e bases de dados de análise não contêm identificadores diretos.

4.5. Armazenamento e segurança

- Dados guardados em dispositivos encriptados, desligados da rede, ou servidores institucionais, sem recurso a serviços de cloud externos.
- Os dados permanecem sob controlo direto da equipa de investigação, em ambiente institucional seguro.

4.6. Acesso e confidencialidade

- O acesso aos dados brutos é restrito à investigadora principal e aos membros designados da equipa nuclear, conforme previsto no protocolo e nos termos definidos no Anexo 10.
- Colaboradores externos (e.g., estudantes na equipa do projeto, colaboradores externos individuais acolhidos na equipa, não prestadores de serviços) apenas podem aceder a dados identificáveis quando tal seja estritamente necessário para tarefas específicas e sempre após assinatura prévia de Termo de Confidencialidade e Responsabilidade (Anexo 9).

4.7. Transferências internacionais

- As transferências internacionais resultam da recolha de dados em países terceiros (EUA, Canadá, Brasil) ou da realização de entrevistas online com participantes nesses países. Tais transferências serão efetuadas em conformidade com o RGPD e sujeitas a salvaguardas adequadas, incluindo, quando aplicável, a utilização de Cláusulas Contratuais-Tipo (SCCs) e/ou o consentimento explícito dos participantes.

4.8. Retenção e eliminação

- Conservação dos dados pessoais até dois anos após o termo do projeto, seguida de eliminação segura.
- A eliminação é realizada pela equipa de investigação, conforme os procedimentos definidos no protocolo.

4.9. Supervisão institucional

- Supervisão pela investigadora principal.

- Submissão do protocolo à Comissão de Ética da ESPP.
- O projeto declara cumprir as regras internas de proteção de dados, designadamente as Orientações aos Investigadores sobre Proteção de Dados Pessoais em Atividades de Investigação Científica do Iscte, bem como as eventuais recomendações da Comissão de Ética e o do Encarregado de Proteção de Dados.

4.10. Medidas específicas no Subprojeto 4

Atendendo ao carácter potencialmente vulnerável da população envolvida no Subprojeto 4, os investigadores preveem um conjunto reforçado de salvaguardas éticas e de proteção de dados (pp. 6–7 do protocolo). Estas incluem: a realização do trabalho apenas após obtenção das aprovações éticas e institucionais locais aplicáveis; o envolvimento de organizações comunitárias, líderes locais e grupos de base como intermediários de confiança e co-criadores do processo de investigação; o co-desenho dos instrumentos de recolha de dados para garantir adequação linguística e cultural; e a mitigação de assimetrias de poder através de sessões de pré-engajamento e da cofacilitação dos focus groups por membros treinados das próprias comunidades.

Estas medidas visam assegurar um enquadramento ético reforçado no trabalho com populações potencialmente vulneráveis e contribuem, simultaneamente e a meu ver, para reforçar o carácter livre e não condicionado do consentimento, no plano da proteção de dados pessoais.

5. Medidas de controlo e mitigação – atividades transversais

As atividades transversais de recolha de dados — web crawling e observação etnográfica presencial e digital — estão igualmente sujeitas a mecanismos específicos de controlo e mitigação definidos pelos investigadores no protocolo.

O tratamento realiza-se exclusivamente para fins de investigação científica, sem utilização comercial ou criação de perfis individuais.

O protocolo prevê ainda que os membros da equipa envolvidos na recolha e tratamento de dados sejam previamente instruídos e recebam formação específica em proteção de dados.

De acordo com o protocolo, aplicam-se as seguintes medidas específicas.

5.1. Web crawling e recolha de dados públicos online

- Atividade limitada à recolha de conteúdos publicamente acessíveis, excluindo informação proveniente de áreas privadas, protegidas por palavra-passe ou sujeitas a restrições técnicas (robots.txt).
- Está prevista a disponibilização de um Aviso de Privacidade e Ética no sítio oficial do projeto, informando sobre as finalidades, categorias de dados, contactos institucionais e direitos dos titulares.

- Quando a notificação direta dos titulares não seja exequível, será invocada a exceção prevista no artigo 14.º, n.º 5, alínea b) do RGPD (esforço desproporcionado), documentada.
- Os dados recolhidos são pseudonimizados e analisados de forma agregada, sem associação a perfis individuais.
- Não são recolhidas categorias especiais de dados, salvo quando tenham sido manifestamente tornadas públicas pelos próprios titulares, nos termos do artigo 9.º, n.º 2, alínea e) do RGPD.

5.2. Observação presencial e digital

- A observação decorre em espaços públicos ou semipúblicos, como conferências, feiras tecnológicas, eventos artísticos ou ativistas, e em espaços online de acesso público.
- Não são recolhidos dados identificativos de forma sistemática; as notas de campo descrevem interações e contextos, sem registo direto de participantes.
- Quando as interações envolvem pessoas em funções públicas ou de representação institucional, poderão ser feitas referências contextuais, em conformidade com o princípio da minimização.
- O protocolo prevê que não sejam realizadas gravações áudio ou vídeo sem consentimento explícito dos intervenientes e estabelece que nunca são registadas conversas privadas.
- As notas de campo são tratadas como dados pseudonimizados, armazenadas de forma segura com os restantes materiais de investigação e sob controlo da equipa do projeto.
- Nos contextos semipúblicos ou organizados, a equipa procede à informação prévia ou solicitação de autorização junto das entidades responsáveis/organizadoras, antes de realizar a observação.

6. Medidas adicionais e propostas de ajustamento

Entende-se recomendar as seguintes medidas complementares ou adicionais, tendo em vista assegurar a conformidade do tratamento com as orientações institucionais do Iscte e consolidar o quadro de segurança, confidencialidade e licitude previsto no projeto:

Sugere-se:

- a) Que as fichas de informação ao participante identifiquem expressamente o Iscte – Instituto Universitário de Lisboa como Responsável pelo Tratamento, em conformidade com o artigo 13.º, n.º 1, alínea a), do RGPD.
- b) Assegurar que as fichas de informação explicitem que a retirada do consentimento não afeta a licitude do tratamento já realizado (em conformidade com o artigo 7.º, n.º 3 do RGPD).

- c) Explicitar nas fichas de informação o endereço eletrónico específico do projeto como contacto para o exercício dos direitos dos titulares e para esclarecimento de dúvidas.
- d) Clarificar a expressão «sem recurso a cloud services», especificando que se refere a serviços de cloud externos. Recomenda-se que, na recolha, armazenamento e tratamento de dados pessoais, sejam utilizadas exclusivamente ferramentas devidamente licenciadas pelo Iscte (por exemplo, Microsoft Teams), assegurando-se que os dados pessoais são armazenados apenas em serviços e servidores institucionais (o que pode incluir, quando aplicável, serviços de computação em nuvem, desde que contratualizados e protegidos pelo Iscte).
- e) Não se considera obrigatória a inclusão, nos formulários de consentimento, de referências a eventuais transferências para os EUA associadas ao uso de plataformas como o Microsoft Teams, desde que se utilizem plataformas licenciadas institucionalmente pelo Iscte (cujo tratamento de dados se encontre já enquadrado nos termos contratuais e nas salvaguardas aplicáveis, incluindo, quando relevante, o EU–US Data Privacy Framework).
- f) Sempre que o Plano de Gestão de Dados preveja a partilha de dados em regime de ciência aberta, essa partilha deve ocorrer apenas após anonimização completa. Recomenda-se incluir nos formulários de consentimento (por conseguinte, antes da anonimização) uma opção específica que permita aos participantes escolher se autorizam ou não a disponibilização pública em regime de ciência aberta dos seus dados anonimizados. O participante deve ser informado desta possibilidade e dispor de uma opção livre e não condicionada de consentir ou recusar essa partilha em regime de ciência aberta. Deve ser identificado o repositório de acesso aberto em questão.
- g) A eventual adoção de Cláusulas Contratuais-Tipo (SCCs) para transferências internacionais deve ser articulada com o Gabinete Jurídico, dado que a sua aplicação exige a análise das garantias oferecidas pela organização importadora e a verificação da conformidade formal dos instrumentos a celebrar.
- h) Caso não se opte ou não seja possível adotar Cláusulas Contratuais-Tipo ou outras garantias adequadas previstas no artigo 46.º do RGPD, a transferência internacional poderá ocorrer com base em consentimento explícito do participante (art. 49.º, n.º 1, alínea a)). Esse consentimento deve incluir a informação de que não é possível assegurar que o país onde ocorre a recolha (ou o país de destino, no caso de exportação de dados) garante um nível de proteção equivalente ao da UE, bem como dos riscos decorrentes da ausência de salvaguardas adequadas.
- i) Sempre que um participante opte por permitir a sua identificação em publicações ou materiais de divulgação científica — em particular no Subprojeto 4, dada a natureza sensível dos dados envolvidos —, recomenda-se que a equipa de investigação realize uma ponderação ética adicional, avaliando os riscos específicos associados ao contexto sociopolítico e à informação partilhada. Esta ponderação poderá ser discutida com o participante, assegurando que a escolha de se identificar é informada, livre e consciente, e que os potenciais impactos (por

exemplo, exposição pública, riscos profissionais, comunitários ou pessoais) são compreendidos.

- j) Os formulários de consentimento, que contêm dados pessoais dos participantes, devem ser armazenados de forma segura, cifrada e separada dos restantes dados de investigação, sendo acessíveis apenas a pessoas autorizadas, e eliminados assim que deixem de ser necessários, mediante pedido do titular ou no momento da eliminação/anonimização dos demais dados pessoais recolhidos no projeto.
- k) Os dados pessoais utilizados para o recrutamento de participantes (por exemplo, e-mails, contactos telefónicos, mensagens, anotações de campo identificadoras) devem ser conservados apenas pelo período estritamente necessário ao processo de recrutamento, devendo ser eliminados após a sua conclusão ou no momento da eliminação/anonimização dos restantes dados pessoais recolhidos no âmbito do projeto.
- l) Recomenda-se a observação e o cumprimento das demais medidas técnicas e organizativas constantes das secções E1 e E2, conforme aplicável, das Orientações aos Investigadores em Atividades de Investigação Científica do Iscte.
- m) Com referência ao último parágrafo da página 2 do protocolo, chama-se a atenção para o facto de que os termos de responsabilidade e confidencialidade não substituem os instrumentos jurídicos exigidos pelo artigo 28.º do RGPD. Caso terceiros, designadamente prestadores de serviços, venham a tratar dados pessoais por conta e sob instruções do Iscte, deverá ser formalizado o respetivo contrato de subcontratação ou instrumento jurídico equivalente, em conformidade com o artigo 28.º do RGPD (distinto do termo de responsabilidade e confidencialidade referido no Anexo 9). Sempre que tal se verifique, deve o projeto solicitar o apoio do GAI, que articulará com o Gabinete Jurídico a preparação dos instrumentos contratuais necessários.
- n) Sugere-se que o teor do Termo de Confidencialidade e Responsabilidade aplicável a colaboradores externos (Anexo 9) seja previamente validado pelo Gabinete Jurídico do Iscte, de modo a assegurar a conformidade formal e material das obrigações assumidas por estes colaboradores no tratamento de dados pessoais.
- o) Recomenda-se que a secção 4 do Anexo 7, relativa ao tratamento posterior dos dados recolhidos por web crawling, seja ajustada para refletir o enquadramento jurídico previsto no RGPD. Tratando-se de operações de tratamento posterior para fins de investigação científica, a base jurídica aplicável resulta da conjugação do artigo 6.º, n.º 1, alínea e), com o artigo 6.º, n.º 4 (que estabelece os critérios de compatibilidade para o tratamento posterior) e com o artigo 89.º, que define as salvaguardas específicas aplicáveis à investigação científica.

7. Conclusões

Em síntese, considera-se que o projeto fAlces apresenta, na documentação submetida, um enquadramento adequado de proteção de dados, incluindo propostas de salvaguardas, procedimentos e medidas organizacionais e técnicas alinhadas com o RGPD e com as orientações institucionais do Iscte. Recomenda-se, contudo, a adoção

das medidas adicionais indicadas na secção 6, das quais dependerá a conformidade efetiva do tratamento.

Assegurada pela equipa a implementação das medidas previstas e das recomendações adicionais aqui formuladas, entende-se estar assegurada a proteção dos dados pessoais e os direitos dos respetivos titulares. Designadamente, considera-se que i) o risco inicial associado ao tratamento — incluindo os riscos acrescidos identificados em determinados subprojetos — é adequadamente mitigado, resultando num risco residual reduzido a um nível aceitável; e ii) o projeto satisfaz os requisitos de licitude, proporcionalidade, segurança e transparência aplicáveis à investigação científica no Iscte.

Nuno David

Encarregado de Proteção de Dados do Iscte

Assinado por: Nuno Manuel
Mendes da Cruz David
Identificação: B108883611
Data: 2025-12-03 às 01:57:45

